

Prafulla Chandra Ray – A Profile[†]

D. Banerjea*

Manuscript received 07 February 2011, accepted 23 February 2011

Prafulla Chandra was born in a well-to-do family in the Khulna district of the then Bengal province of India on August 2, 1861. After his school and college education at Calcutta he went to Edinburg University (Scotland, Great Britain) with a prestigious Gilchrist Scholarship in the year 1882 to pursue higher studies in chemistry. Early in life, during his school days, Prafulla Chandra developed great passion for History, Languages and Literature which blossomed further in his later life even after he became a Chemist by destiny and actively and fruitfully pursued this career of an educationist and research worker in Chemistry for almost 50 years, first in the Presidency College at Calcutta from 1889 and then in the newly founded University College of Science of Calcutta University from 1916 as the first Sir Taraknath Palit Professor and Head of the Department of Chemistry. He retired from this official position in the year 1936 but continued as Emeritus Professor till the end of his life (June 16, 1944)

Prafulla Chandra was a linguist having proficiency in several languages including Sanskrit, Latin, Greek, German and French, apart from his great command of English and Bengali, and had a remarkable skill and competence to express his views on various diverse issues in an extremely lucid style. Commenting on his autobiographical memoir "Life and Experiences of a Bengali Chemist", Dr. H. E. Armstrong said, "... from the beginning to the end the message of the book is one of highest endeavour – pulsating with vitality and intellectual force."

Prafulla Chandra was a prolific writer and an in-depth reading of his numerous articles in both English and Bengali languages gives us an insight into the diverse traits of his personality and character. In this short article an attempt has been made to present a glimpse of his multifaceted personality.

Prafulla Chandra was a Scientist, Educationist, Hu-

manist, Philanthropist, Rationalist, Nationalist and Patriot – all per excellence – of whom his contemporary Sir Jagadish Chandra Bose said,

"The combination of such qualities in a single individual is indeed rare there can be no higher example for the young generation to emulate . "

"There is in Sir P. C. Ray the element of vigorous action which knows no rest."

The truth of the above citations is evident from the many diverse activities in which Prafulla Chandra engaged himself and which he pursued with relentless vigour.

Prafulla Chandra had his characteristic teaching style. He used to start his lectures with some pleasantries and imperceptibly drew his students to the subject matter of the lecture made interesting with experimental demonstrations and also explaining the background of scientific developments. His lectures usually concluded with observations on social evils like superstition, irrational rituals, orthodoxy, etc. In his own words, "To be a successful teacher especially to junior students, who are just commencing a course in elementary chemistry, it is essential that he should have a neat hand in conducting experiments and that these should be so arranged as to make the lectures not only interesting but also easily intelligible "

Swami Vivekananda said, "Education is the manifestation of perfection in Man". The nine alphabets of the word EDUCATION signify the qualities of an ideal person and Prafulla Chandra was in ample possession of all these, viz.,

E = Enlightenment; D = Discipline, Dedication, Devotion; U = Understanding; C = Critical; A = Agility, Active; T = Truthful, Tenacity, Tolerance; I = Integrity; O = Objectivity; N = Nobility.

Referring to the qualities of a scientist Michael Faraday said,

[†]In Commemoration of the 150th Birth Anniversary of Acharya Prafulla Chandra Ray.

*Sir Rashbehary Ghose Professor of Chemistry (Retired), Calcutta University. *E-mail* : banerjeas2005@yahoo.co.in

“A scientist should be a man willing to listen to every suggestion, be able to judge for himself. He should not be biased by appearances, have no favourite hypotheses, be of no school, and in doctrine have no master. He should not be a respecter of persons, but of things. Truth shall be his primary object. If to these qualities be added industry he may hope to walk within the veil of the temple of nature.”

We see these qualities amply in Prafulla Chandra. In his personal habits Prafulla Chandra exemplified Spartan simplicity. Like the sages of ancient India his motto was, *Plain Living and High Thinking*.

He was extremely frugal in spending for himself but was very generous in charity to the needy. While in service in the Presidency College, Calcutta, he used to spend over 90% of his salary in charity, and after joining the University College of Science of Calcutta University in 1916 at the request of the then Vice-Chancellor of Calcutta University, Sir Asutosh Mookerjee, he donated to the University his salary for a major period (1922-36) of his service for the purpose of setting up of a modern research laboratory for Inorganic Chemistry and also instituting a Fellowship for research in the Chemistry Department of the University of Calcutta. On one occasion a student of his (Priyadarajan Ray) received a forceful thrashing on his back for bringing for his Guru (Respected Teacher) a quarter seer (*ca.* 230g) of delicious grapes spending four annas (25 paise, a quarter of a Rupee). But the same day a few hours later Prafulla Chandra did not hesitate to donate a large part of his bank balance to an organisation engaged in social and charitable work. Speaking of him Mahatma Gandhi (M. K. Gandhi) said (1931),

“It took my breath away when I heard that out of his princely salary he kept only a few Rupees for himself and the rest he devoted to public use, particularly for helping poor students.”

With all his shares in different companies he created a trust to offer financial assistances to needy widows.

Prafulla Chandra was not an ivory-tower scientist and was always ready to help the distressed and the oppressed. During the catastrophic floods of Bengal in the year 1923 his office in the University College of Science, Calcutta, became the headquarters for the organisation of relief work on a war footing, assisted by a band of his devoted pupils and followers including Netaji Subhas Chandra Bose, Meghnad Saha and others. Commenting on the flood situation and Sir P. C. Ray's role in organising relief

work, a British correspondent wrote in the “Manchester Guardian” (November 11, 1923) as follows :

“When the calamity occurred the Government were above flood level in the hills of Darjeeling They were slow to move, and the action taken was inadequate In these circumstances a Professor of Chemistry, Sir P. C. Ray, stepped forward and called upon his countrymen to make good the Government's omissions the enthusiasm of the response to the appeal was largely to Sir P. C. Ray's remarkable personality and position He is a very strong nationalist He is also a real organiser and a real teacher. I heard a European saying, “If Mr. Gandhi had only been able to create two more Sir P. C. Ray's he would have succeeded in getting *swaraj* within a year.... When Sir P. C. Ray calls everyone knows that the money will be spent and well spent, and not wasted.”

Prafulla Chandra took active part on several other similar occasion also and Mahatma Gandhi affectionately referred to him as the “Doctor of Floods”, and Sir Asutosh called him “guardian angel of the suffering humanity”.

Prafulla Chandra had very strong views on social evils, customs, rituals, superstition and orthodoxy, and this is evident from many of his acts, deeds and utterances and what he had expressed in his numerous articles. One day he entered the class room at Presidency College in an agitated state of mind, and pointing to the students he said, “Each one of you is a potential murderer.” Realizing that the students were puzzled by his outburst he said that in the newspaper that morning he read a news that a young girl committed suicide as her father did not have the means to meet the dowry demands of the parents of the prospective groom for her marriage. In his class lectures also he used to discuss at the end about the prevailing social evils to make the students aware of the gravity of the problem. In an article speaking on untouchability and cast divisions he said,

“We forget that in the days of our glory the stringency of the cast system was unknown. Vyasa, the great compiler of the *Vedas* was born of a fisherwoman. Ramachandra (Lord Rama) was not ashamed to embrace the Chandala (a low cast person) Guhaka as his most intimate friend, Srikrishna (Lord Krishna) in his infancy was reared up by a cow-woman (of cowherd community). Why were these great men not outcasted and spurned away as untouchables?”

“Concepts such as “I shall not marry your daughter”, “I shall not accept food of you”, “If I dine with you I

shall be outcasted”, “If I tread upon your very shadow I shall become impure”, and all such ideas and concepts have wrought havoc in our society and our progress.”

He believed in Swami Vivekananda’s words,

“A religion that does not feel for the miseries of the poor, which does not uplift man, forfeits the name of religion.”

On the system of *Kulinism* in Bengal he wrote in an article as follows :

“We may give credit to those who were responsible for the institution of *Kulinism* when they made it a reward for personal merit and intellectual and moral attainments. But when *Kulinism* became hereditary the Bengali sank deeper and deeper in the mire of degradation ... The division of the Bengali society into numerous sects and sub-sects was a logical outcome of *Kulinism* and a multitude of evils wrought by this system.”

Speaking on orthodox views and superstition he said,

“I used to place on the table (in the class lecture room) a sample of burnt bone, which now had nothing to do with the sources they came from The burnt bone is almost a pure chemical compound phosphate of calcium which is prescribed as a nerve tonic. I would often, put a bit of the burnt bone in my mouth and chew it and even swallow it and invite my pupils to do the same.”

“India had glorious period and she has not always been under the domination of the *Shastras*. Rationalism and the spirit of inquiry were the redeeming features of ancient India. The sage Kapila went to the extent of questioning the very existence of God as it cannot be proved by demonstration. Charvaka went a step further and said that “the *Vedas* with their descriptions of the heaven and hell are the creations of the fertile imagination of a few rogues and imposters who secured an easy means of earning their livelihood by working upon the fears and superstitions and the credulity of the prince and the people at large. As these wily priests themselves presided at the Vedic rites and ceremonies (*yajna*), their offices became indispensable and they thereby amassed wealth and support of their families in comfort. These imposters had the hardihood to assert that the animals which are sacrificed in the *yajnas* are transported to the Heav-

ens. If these rogues really had faith in their assertions why they did not decapitate their own parents and offered them as sacrifices?.

“I am as proud of the glories of the Hindus of old days as anybody..... What I want to point out is that by our unquestioned acquiescence in the wisdom of the sages of the past, by regulating our every-day life according to the inflexible rules of the *Smritis* our social fabric has been brought to stagnation and decay.....”

Prafulla Chandra was an ardent believer in discipline in one’s life. One day a person came to meet him beyond the normal visiting hour and his attendant refused to let him in but later relented on hearing that the visitor was Prafulla Chandra’s uncle’s son. After the person left Prafulla Chandra asked his attendant as to why he allowed the visitor at that time. On hearing the attendant’s reply he said, henceforth even my siblings be not allowed if they do not come during the visiting hours (*Asamay babato bhai ele o dekha hobe na*).

Within his frail body he had a steel frame of mind that never failed to respond strongly against all acts of injustice and impropriety. On the pursued education policy of the Government he said,

“The present policy penalises the intellectual activities, specially the pursuit of science, among our countrymen..... The denial of a suitable career takes away all the incentives for a specialised study of science.”

In the month of December, 1922, in the meeting of the Senate of the Calcutta University, he infuriatedly spoke very eloquently and strongly against some conditions imposed by the Government in releasing a grant-in-aid to the University :

“It seems to me, Sir, that there is an unseen hand working from behind with dark and sinister purposes since the year 1912 onwards.... I think we had better shown a bold front. The conditions which have been imposed are so humiliating, so gallingly derogatory to our self-respect, that we had better close down the concern, lock up the gates of the university and go about the country for support. Let the Government abdicate its functions. I must play the role of a professional beggar. A grave crisis is looming large in the horizon of our national disaster. So it behoves us to take concerted action and try our best to avert the calamity; we should gird up our loins and see that the noble heritage which has been granted to us is not

bartered for a mess of pottage. I feel very strongly on this occasion. In the evening of my life I thought I might hand down to our successors the lamp which we have been able to light so dimly, so that it might burn up brilliantly. That feeble light is about to be extinguished. That it why I have not been able to keep my vow of silence. We shall not go down on our knees, we are not to cry *peccavi*. We are not charity boys. We are not Oliver Twists.”

Incidentally, at the same Senate meeting the then Vice-Chancellor Sir Asutosh Mookerjee, another spirited person, who was a pioneer in creating facilities for modern higher education in the country, said, “... Freedom first, freedom second, nothing else shall satisfy me.” Prafulla Chandra was a true nationalist and a patriot ever since his student days at Edinburgh where he wrote the articles, “India Before and After the Mutiny” and “Essays on India” in which he criticised the policies of the British rulers in India. While these made him famous among the apolitical intellectuals of Great Britain, he earned considerable displeasure of the British Government. So when he returned to India from Edinburgh in July 1888 with a coveted D.Sc. degree of Edinburgh University he had to wait for almost a year and thereafter received a rather humiliating offer for a temporary post of an Assistant Professor at Presidency College, Calcutta on a pay of Rs. 250 per month and not that of a Professor in the Indian Education Service (IES) (pay scale of Rs. 700-50-1000) despite being qualified for the same. In response to his representation in the matter to the Director of Public Instruction of the Government, the D.P.I. told him that if he was a clever chemist he should start industries so that he could employ men of the qualification of the D.P.I. as his assistants. This challenge Prafulla Chandra fulfilled later by setting up the Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works. But since he was undaunted and determined to fulfil his objective and mission in life, he joined the Presidency College, Calcutta, on June 15, 1889 in the offered post. After a period of seven years when he had two papers published based on research work he started at Presidency College his scientific talent received the attention of the Government and he was promoted to the post of a Professor in the Provincial Educational Service in the pay scale of Rs. 400-700 per month but was asked to join the Government College at Rajsahi as Principal which he declined as that would have deprived him of his opportunities of carrying on his research activities for

which he had created facilities, fighting against heavy odds. The Government ultimately relented and allowed him to continue in the higher post of Professor at Presidency College, Calcutta.

This episode shows his dedication and devotion to science that he was ready to sacrifice a higher post and a higher pay just to be able to carry on with his research activities. During the next 15 years he published some 40 research papers, mostly jointly with his several co-workers, and he was then placed in the Indian Education Service (IES) in the year 1911. But an inspection of civil list shows he was never promoted to a permanent post in the IES, and the placement was an officiating one with an additional personal pay of Rs. 100 per month which was increased to Rs. 150 per month in the year 1915. At the request of Sir Asutosh Mookerjee, Vice-Chancellor of Calcutta University, he joined the newly established University College of Science as the first Sir Tarak Nath Palit Professor and Head of the Department of Chemistry on deputation from Government service in the month of November, 1916 and permanently thereafter after retirement from Government service in the year 1917.

Prafulla Chandra had the capacity to quickly recognise the quality and talent of a person and this we see in his picking up one Jitendra Nath Rakshit as his assistant and co-worker, although Rakshit did not have the formal university degree as he failed to pass the B.Sc. examination of Calcutta University. With Rakshit he published quite a few research papers and used to refer him as his “precious find”. This reminds us of Humphrey Davy who took Michael Faraday as his assistant and later spoke of him as his “greatest discovery”. As desired by him, two of his students Priyadarshan Ray and Jnanendra Nath Mukherjee carried out research and published their work independently from the beginning.

His patriotism and passion for history prompted him to undertake the most arduous job of collecting materials from not quite readily available sources and documenting these systematically into the two volume treatise “A History of Hindu Chemistry” (vol. 1, 1902, vol. 2, 1909 published by the Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works, Calcutta) the second revised editions of which were published subsequently (vol. 1, 1904 by William Norgate, London, and vol. 2, 1925 by Chatterjee and Co. Ltd., Calcutta). In this treatise he furnished convincing evidences of the advances in chemical and medical sciences in ancient India and its progress

over a period of *ca.* 2500 B.C. to *ca.* 1600 A.D. (see **Appendix**). This has been further revised and brought out as a single volume by the Indian Chemical Society in the year 1956, under the Editorship of one of Sir P. C. Ray's most trusted pupils Professor Priyadarajan Ray, with a more appropriate title of "History of Chemistry in Ancient and Medieval India". This change of title was necessary as there were significant contributions made by several Buddhist scholars (like Nagarjuna, Vagbhata and others) and several Jains as well (the Jains made notable contributions in developing the concepts of atoms, molecules, chemical combination, etc.) (For an account of all such developments see "Progress of Chemistry in Ancient and Medieval India and its Impact on Medicine", D. Banerjea, 4th Hasi Majumdar Memorial Oration, Calcutta University, March 17, 2008, published by Calcutta University).

On one occasion while delivering a lecture at Lahore University (now in Pakistan) on the contributions of ancient Indians in the field of Chemistry with illustrations using charts and models of the types of apparatus used then for performing chemical operations, he was very much annoyed noticing expressions of sneer in a young Englishman present in the audience. Hence, before concluding he took a sample of *Makaradhwaj* (red refined variety of mercury sulfide, *vermilion*) in his palm and said that his ancestors made this remarkable chemical, which was often prescribed even by the European physicians of his time, as a curative for various types of illness and for rejuvenation several centuries earlier when the ancestors of the young Englishman were roaming in jungles, wearing raw hides.

By the first decade of the 20th century Prafulla Chandra's fame as an educationist and scientist spread far and wide and as a consequence several recognitions and honour came to him during the next few years, viz., Honorary Doctorate degree from Calcutta University (1908), Durham University (1912) and a few years later from Dacca University (now in Bangladesh) and Benaras Hindu University. He was bestowed Honorary Fellowship of the Chemical Society, London, and of the Deutsche (German) Academy, Munich (in 1934). The British Government that ignored him so far conferred Companionship of the Order of the Indian Empire (CIE) in 1911 and Knighted him in the year 1919. He was elected General President of the Indian Science Congress (1920), first President of the Indian Chemical Society (1924), Founda-

tion Fellow of the Indian National Science Academy (1935) and first President of the Indian Science News Association (1935). Despite his patriotism he never joined in active political movement, although on some occasion he addressed meetings organised by the Indian National Congress and had the fullest sympathies for those who took active part in Indian Freedom Movements.

Despite being a nationalist to the core Prafulla Chandra was totally opposed to emotionalism and any act of destruction of national properties and resources. In the days of the *Swadeshi Movement* of 1905 against the Government's act of partitioning Bengal, the National Council of Education was established in the month of March, 1906, at Jadavpur by a band of idealists for imparting education on national lines and under national control. Being in Government service Prafulla Chandra could not take active part by becoming one of its founder members but served indirectly in various ways. After his retirement from Government service he became a member of the organisation in the year 1919, was elected its Honorary Rector in the year 1922 and then President in 1924 and continued in this capacity till the last day of his life.

In the year 1919 a public meeting was held in the Town Hall at Calcutta under the chairmanship of (*Deshbandhu*) C. R. Das in protest of the Rowlatt Act. At this meeting, at the request of C. R. Das, Prafulla Chandra briefly spoke and said, although he was a man of the laboratory, he felt that "there are occasions which demanded that he should leave the test tube to attend to the call of the country. Science can wait, *Swaraj* cannot".

During the Indian Freedom Movement when C. R. Das was imprisoned Prafulla Chandra wrote to his wife Smt. Basanti Devi where he said as follows :

"... I can assure you, however, dear sister, that in serving my favourite science I have only one idea in mind, namely, that through her I should serve my country. Our aspirations are the same. God knows, I have no other object in mind"

Since 1931 Prafulla Chandra had close association with the two top political leaders Gokhale and Gandhi. He was a strong believer in the philosophy of Mahatma Gandhi and his advocacy of spinning with the *Charkha*. But he was equally sympathetic to Netaji Subhas Chandra Bose. For his advocacy of *Charkha* spinning as a means for economic upliftment of the common man he faced much

criticism, from Rabindranath Tagore. Despite his support of the Gandhian policies in general he had sharp differences with Mahatma Gandhi in the latter's policy to involve Indians in the *Khilafat* movement and he openly expressed this :

“We must not allow our loyalty to the mother country be swamped by the wave of extra-territorial patriotism.... India must not be a spike in the *Khilafat* wheel gyrated from Istambul. The *Swaraj* of India must be our all compelling goal

Prafulla Chandra had the vision to realise that progress of India and of Indians can only be possible through education and economic prosperity of the masses and for the latter commerce and industry are essential, and that Chemistry can play a major role for the country's industrial and economic progress. This actually prompted him in his college days to take up Chemistry for higher studies despite his keen interest in History, Languages and Literature. The lectures of Sir Alexander Pedler at Presidency College that he regularly used to attend in his student days also created interest in and inspiration for Chemistry learning. After joining Presidency College in the teaching post he seriously thought of utilising his knowledge in Chemistry to set up a Chemical Industry. To begin with he started making commonly used medicinal concoctions and tonics in his rented house procuring the component chemicals from the local market and even making some of these, all this single-handed. The Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works (BCPW) of the future thus had its modest beginning in the year 1892, and this ultimately became a regular registered company in the year 1901 with which he remained actively associated as a Member of the Board of Directors, but unlike the other members he never took any share out of the company's profit. But in the year 1939 he resigned from the Board due to sharp differences with the other members who became more interested and showing ravenous appetite for getting a large share of the dividends without caring for the well-being and financial viability of the company. On being requested to withdraw his resignation Prafulla Chandra in his characteristic style replied as follows :

“It is indeed very kind and generous on the part of the Directors and their extending alms to a beggar's bowl. But I am naturally reminded of the story of the dacoits who having plundered a household after having gagged the inmates and then tied their hand and foot were decamping with the booty when an old woman, who somehow or other concealed herself, exclaimed, “You are carrying away everything leaving nothing behind”.

Whereupon, the dacoits, out of pity threw her a few pieces of torn cloths and a few annas (anna = 1/16 of a Rupee) in the bargain.”

“This story points to a moral and adorns my tale My joining the Board is out of question, specially in view of their attitude towards the research work I am glad I can wash my hands clean of all responsibility in the matter of the failure of the Bengal Chemical”

“The fixed running idea of yours and the Directors had always been to squeeze out everything (like sugarcane) as long as they could offer large dividends.”

He signed this letter describing his position as an “Evicted and homeless stranger in the land (i.e., B.C.P.W.) he once called his own.” In his resignation letter Prafulla Chandra had bitterly complained of the management's total lack of concern as to the need of a reserve fund and that how his repeated advice to the management to induct professional scientists as members of the Board of Directors instead of packing it with incapacitated persons, spend more on research and development and diversify production instead of continuing as a manufacturer of only toilet preparations, tinctures and cotton gauze fell into deaf years. This shows his foresight even at that age (78 years).

The great Chinese Philosopher Confucius said, “Fools despise wise counsel”, Prafulla Chandra's predictions about the future of Bengal Chemical and Pharmaceutical Works became true since the company had later to be closed down as a sick unit for years till its take-over and revival by the Government of India.

Prafulla Chandra had association with several other commercial ventures also as their patrons, viz., Bengal Potteries, Bengal Enamel, National Tanneries, a weighing machine manufacturing unit, an Indian shipping company and a publishing house (Chuckerverty, Chatterjee & Co. Ltd.). Contrary to what had often, been said by people of other states of India, that Prafulla Chandra had concern only for Bengal and the Bengalees, he had fullest sympathy for any Indian commercial venture irrespective of whether it was in Bengal or in any other region of India. In this connection it would be worth mentioning an incident narrated by the renowned physicist Dr. M. N. Saha (summarised below) :

After the first world war the Sciendia Steam Navigation Co., one of the pioneer Indian shipping concerns, had engaged a vessel to take passengers to Europe. The passengers were mostly Indians and P. C. Ray

was one of them. Most of the other passengers were young boys from Bengal and other provinces of India going to England for higher studies (M. N. Saha was one of them). A few British I.C.S. officers were also there as they could not get passage in boats of European companies as these were booked to full capacity. But the British officials were not at all happy that an Indian company shall enter into competition with European companies in the shipping or any other commercial venture. So they spread a rumour about poor quality of food and service on board and instigated some of the young Indian passengers to draft and sign a petition to the authorities to cancel the permit granted to the Indian company. Some Indian students brought the petition to P. C. Ray also for his signature. After reading the petition Prafulla Chandra realised that the young boys were motivatedly instigated as they had no knowledge of the quality of service and food offered in ships run by European companies. He told the boys that from his personal knowledge he can assert that there is no genuine cause for complaint and explained to them what motivated the British officers to instigate them. The young boys realised their mistake and with their consent Prafulla Chandra tore the petition to pieces and threw these into the sea.

This shows that Prafulla Chandra's patriotism was not confined within the narrow limits of provincialism. A *swadeshi* venture, whether from Bengal or Bombay was equally dear to him.

Prafulla Chandra had great admiration for young people engaged in the pursuit of science and they always received from him encouragement of all sorts. In the year 1929 (before the announcement of award of Nobel Prize to Sir C. V. Raman) he spoke of C. V. Raman as follows :

“My colleague Raman is a host in himself If this temple of science had produced just one Raman and nothing else it will have amply justified the expectations of its founder.”

After getting his B.Sc. degree from Edinburgh University Prafulla Chandra expressed to his teacher Professor Alexander Crum Brown that he wished to pursue research work in a specialised field to become a Physical Chemist. To this Professor Crum Brown said, “...be a chemist first and a physical chemist afterwards.” Prafulla Chandra remembered this advice throughout his life. Hence, after returning to India in 1888, after being admitted to the D.Sc. degree of Edinburgh University, when he joined

Presidency College, Calcutta, in 1889 and started his active research career that he continued in his subsequent assignment in the University College of Science, Calcutta, we find him engaged in carrying out research work in all the conventional areas of chemistry, the results of which he published in several of the leading international journals, and after the foundation of the Indian Chemical Society in 1924 most of his research papers were published in the *Journal of the Indian Chemical Society* as well. His last research papers were published in the year 1936, one of which was in the very prestigious journal *Nature*, published from London. Constraints of space does not permit an elaborate discussion of his research contributions and only a broad overview may be given. His first noteworthy success was the reported discovery (1896) of mercurous nitrite published in the *Journal of the Asiatic Society of Bengal*, **65**, 1-9 (1896) and *Zeit. Anorg. Chem.*, **12**, 365-74 (1896), and a report on the varying conditions under which the nitrites of mercury are formed (*J. Chem. Soc.*, **71**, 337-44 (1897)). This discovery received much applause of renowned chemists of Europe of that time and the journal *Nature* mentioned of this as follows :

“The *Journal of the Asiatic Society* can scarcely be said to have a place in our chemical libraries; the current number, however, contains a paper by Dr. P. C. Ray of Presidency College, Calcutta, on mercurous nitrite that is worthy of note” (*Nature*, 1896).

But the existence of mercurous nitrite has been disproved many years later (R. A. Potts and A. L. Allred, *Inorg. Chem.*, **5**, 1066 (1966); cf., “Comprehensive Inorganic Chemistry”, vol. 3, Ch. 30, p. 293, (Eds.) J. C. Bailar, Jr., H. J. Emeleus, R. S. Nyholm and A. F. Trotman-Dickerson, Pergamon Press, Oxford, 1973/75). An estimate of the enthalpy of formation of authentic mercurous nitrite, based on thermochemical data available in literature, shows this to be highly endothermic which accounts for its non-existence (D. Banerjea, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, **81**, 1018 (2004)). During 1924 to 1934 he published a few papers (in *J. Indian Chem. Soc.* and *Zeit. Anorg. Allgm. Chem.*) on what he described as compounds of gold and of platinum in sub-normal/abnormal valence states with astounding suggestions of their constitution as he had no access to the modern techniques for structure elucidation. A close look into the analytical compositions of many of these seems to indicate that several of these could be typical metal cluster compounds as we know of now in cases of gold, platinum and many other cases. This requires an investigation of the structures of these com-

pounds by the available modern techniques, and if this way it is shown that these are indeed metal cluster compounds then that would establish Prafulla Chandra as a pioneer in the field and that would perhaps be his most outstanding research contribution.

In any assessment of his research contributions we must keep in mind the constraints of lack of adequate facilities and resources as well as his multidimensional activities that took away much of his time; collecting materials for the stupendous task of compiling the "A History of Hindu Chemistry", vols. 1 and 2 (*loc. cit.*) being one of these, apart from his engagement in various social and relief work. Judged in this context his overall output of research documented in some 158 published papers many of which were in reputed international journals like *J. Chem. Soc.* (London), *Zeit. Anorg. Chem.* (Germany), *Nature* (London) is surely commendable. His first research paper based on his work on the conjugated double sulfates of metals, which he did for his D.Sc. thesis, was published in the *Proceedings of the Royal Society* (Edinburgh) in 1888, pp. 267-283.

In this connection it would be worth noting the following observations of one of his pupils Professor J. N. Mukherjee and another of a grand-pupil Dr. S. S. Bhatnagar :

"Outweighing his achievements as a scientific worker the creation and fostering of the Indian School of Chemistry will ever remain his conspicuous contributions towards national progress of Indians." – J. N. Mukherjee (1961)

"If a census were to be taken of all the Indian chemists who have published any original work and if they were asked to indicate the source of their inspiration, I believe the majority would ascribe the credit to Sir P. C. Ray.... The one atrocious crime which I have committed is that I am not his pupil. My defence is I happen to be a grand-pupil of his." – S. S. Bhatnagar (1928).

The above citations sum up very appropriately the most outstanding contribution of Sir P. C. Ray as an educationist and scientist in establishing an active school of research. There was a time when one could see products of his school at the helm of affairs in teaching and research in various parts of India of that time. He not only patronized young men working in chemistry but in other branches of science as well, two outstanding examples of such persons being Professor M. N. Saha and Professor S. N. Bose.

In the year 1931 the citizens of Calcutta arranged a meeting on a grand scale in the Town Hall at Calcutta to felicitate Sir P. C. Ray. The meeting was attended by all the elites and eminent persons including Rabindranath Tagore, NL. In his address Tagore spoke eloquently of Prafulla Chandra. His speech was delivered in Bengali and its essence may be expressed in English as follows :

..... It is said in the *Upanisad*, the Supreme Creator said, I shall become many in my creations; this urge for self dispersal is at the root of creation. It is through such natural creative urge that Prafulla Chandra became many in his pupils....

Indeed several of his students who took up positions of responsibility in universities and institutions in different regions of India, many of whom earned fame by their scientific contributions, were thus responsible for the propagation and dissemination of scientific knowledge to which they were initiated by Prafulla Chandra. This creation of an active school was his unique contribution to science in India and in this respect he was much more fortunate than all his eminent contemporaries, although their individual contributions in the field of science were of a high order.

Although his 70th birthday was celebrated on a grand scale, his 80th birthday went almost unnoticed as by that time he became practically a forgotten hero and remained so till his demise on June 16, 1944. The Indian Chemical Society was founded in the year 1924 (registered on May 24, 1924) through the efforts and initiatives of his few pupils and admirers and he was the first President of the Society and was elected for a second term which privilege none of his successors have enjoyed. It was his inspiration that was behind this bold venture. On the occasion of the founding of the Society and his assuming the office of the President, he received a message of congratulation from Professor Wynne, President of the Chemical Society, London, to which Prafulla Chandra replied as follows :

"More than 40 years ago, while a student at Edinburgh, I almost dreamt a dream that God willing, a time would come when modern India would also be in a position to contribute her quota to the world's stock of scientific knowledge, and it has been good fortune to see my dream materialize."

It is perhaps not known to many that Prafulla Chandra

donated a sum of Rs. 10,000 (a decent amount in those days) to the University of Calcutta for construction of two rooms in the Sir Taraknath Palit building in the University College of Science for a “permanent habitation” for the Indian Chemical Society (reported in the August 3, 1929 issue of a prominent English newspaper of that time, *Amrita Bazar Patrika*). For several years the journal published by the Society was enriched by the contributions of Prafulla Chandra and his co-workers and pu-

pils. While we shall never be able to repay our debt to him, we must try to emulate and propagate his ideals and this would be the fittest way to offer our homage to him.

In conclusion, it is worth quoting what Educationist and a renowned Member of the Indian Parliament (Late) Hiren Mukherjee said of him :

“His life is a heap of treasure that neither moth nor rust can corrupt and even our unworthiness of his legacy can sully.”

Appendix

Origin and Progress of Chemistry in Ancient and Medieval India – A Summary (For a fuller account see “History of Chemistry in Ancience and Medieval India (Incorporating Sir P. C. Ray’s *A History of Hindu Chemistry*”, (Ed.) P. Ray, Indian Chemical Society, Calcutta, 1956; “Progress of Chemistry in Ancient and Medieval India and its Impact on Medicine”, D. Banerjea, Calcutta University, 2008 and references cited therein).

In Europe Chemistry had its nebulous origin only during the 12th century A.D. when Theophilus recognised some chemical processes with further developments in the period of Alchemy when Roger Bacon (1214-1294), a renowned Alchemist, emphasised the importance of experiments and observations, followed by the Iatrochemical period when Paracelsus (1493-1541) freed Chemistry and Medicine from the clutches of the Alchemist. This was followed by Francis Bacon’s (1561-1636) contributions that laid the foundation of modern science. It is Robert Boyle (1627-1691) who is credited for ushering in modern chemistry by his realisation of different gases as different species and recognition of the distinction between elements, compounds and mixtures, apart from being propounder of the Gas laws for which he is generally known. It was the work of the renowned French Chemist A. L. Lavoisier (1733-1804) that demonstrated the role of oxygen in combustion which thereby demolished the *Phlogiston Theory* of Stahl (1660-1734) based on Becher’s postulate (1667) of a *combustion principle* in all combustible materials which is responsible for their combustion, that is rightly recognised as the beginning of modern Inorganic Chemistry.

Evidence, however, points to the fact that human race

of pre-historic India, since *ca.* 3rd millenium B.C. acquired considerable skill in carrying out operations which involved what we know today as Chemistry. These were surely based on knowledge which these primitive people acquired mostly through accidental observations, but they used the knowledge for the benefit of the people displaying a rational attitude, which is a feature of true scientific spirit.

Archaeological finds from sites of earliest human settlements in Baluchistan, Sind, Punjab and Rajasthan have furnished evidence that these ancient people as early as *ca.* 2700-2500 B.C. were capable of making fairly high quality of wheel-turned burnt potteries (see Figs. 1 and 2), terracotta objects and metallic copper. No copper objects have been found in more ancient sits *ca.* 3000 B.C., which showed only potteries, and another site of a still earlier period (*ca.* 3700 B.C.) yielded only stone implements.

Developments in science (including chemistry and medical science) in India as well as elsewhere in the world was the outcome of natural human instincts for self-preservation, urge to develop practical arts to meet the needs of life and the urge for gaining knowledge. On the developments of science in ancient India it has been said,

“Apart from the rigorous scientific method and practical recipes, Hindu Chemistry was genuinely positively scientific.”– B. N. Seal, “Positive Sciences of the Ancient Hindus”, London, 1915.

Some of the landmark developments in the field of Chemistry and Medicine as were made in ancient and medieval India are summarised in Table 1; some of the corresponding developments in Europe are in Table 2 for comparison.

Table 1. An overview of developments in Chemistry in India (ca. 2500 B.C. to 1600 A.D.)
(Tantric period (alchemy), 700-1300 A.D., Iatrochemical period, 1300-1600 A.D.)

ca. 2500 B.C. to 2000 B.C.	Gold, silver, copper, lead, bronze, electrum (Au-Ag), some minerals, glazed potteries, porcelain, terracotta, <i>faience</i> , art of dyeing (with extract of madder root, alizarin), mortar.
ca. 1500 B.C. to 800 B.C.	Tin, iron, glass, fermentation (for alcoholic drinks and curd), tanning. Emergence of medicinal chemistry (<i>Ayurveda</i>).
ca. 600 B.C. to 400 B.C.	Brass, steel, coloured glasses, solder (Pb-Sn), ink, vegetable dyes, amalgams, diamond and gemstones. Atomic theory and concept of compound formation.
ca. 100 A.D. to 400 A.D.	Theory of chemical combination, alkalis (mild, medium, strong) and their preparation, use of minerals in medicine. Realisation of relation between heat and chemical change.
ca. 400 A.D. to 600 A.D.	Iron pillar (in Delhi) of pure wrought iron and the statue of Goutam Buddha made of pure metallic copper (99.7%) (at Sultanganj) demonstrate the skill in metallurgy and workmanship. Processes for hardening of steel, arsenic, mordants in dyeing, cosmetics and perfumes, gemstones.
ca. 800 A.D. to 900 A.D.	Extraction of zinc from calamine (first in the world), use of mercury sulfide (red and black varieties) in medicine, advanced knowledge of gemstones.
ca. 1000 A.D.	Paper making.
ca. 1100 A.D. to 1200 A.D.	Soap, indelible ink, sulfuric acid, antimony from stibnite.
ca. 1300 A.D. to 1600 A.D.	Calomel and its medicinal uses, blended perfumes of superior quality, aqua regia, gunpowder, pyrotechny. use of essential oils, tinctures, opium, etc., in medicine, <i>bidery</i> (Cu-Pb-Zn-Sn).

Table 2. Some of the developments in Europe
(For India see Table 1)

Discovery	Period
Glass	ca. 12th century A.D. (ca. 2000 B.C. in Egypt, ca. 2600 B.C. in Mesopotamia)
Alchemy	13th century A.D. (2nd century B.C. in China, 1st-7th century in Egypt, since 7th century A.D. in Arabia)
Arsenic	13th century A.D.
Iron	14th century A.D.
Antimony	1492 A.D.
Sulfuric acid	15th century A.D.
Zinc	1695 A.D. (Hamburg), 1740 A.D. (Bristol)
Dyeing (using extract of madder)	18th century A.D. (France)

Fig. 1. Potteries from some pre-Harappan settlements : (a) Polychrome wares (Nal) of Red, Blue, Green and Yellow colours. (b) Potteries (Amri) of Buff and Pink colours.

In the year 2007 archaeologists unearthed a mask made of gold and a gold ring along with silver and bronze vessels from the tomb of a Thracian king, who ruled towards the end of the 4th century B.C., from a place in Bulgaria and this appears to be the earliest use of gold in Europe. But gold coins were in use in Egypt since ca. 3400 B.C. and Indians were familiar with gold at least since ca. 2500 B.C. Similarly, silver extraction by some sort of cupellation started in Europe (in Spain) in ca. 1500 A.D., but in Egypt and Asia Minor in ca. 3000 B.C. and in India in ca. 2500 B.C. There is a fine Chaldean vase of pure silver of ca. 2850 B.C. in the Louvre Museum in Paris.

Indus Valley Civilization (Harappan Culture) (ca. 2500-1500 B.C.; 2300-1700 B.C. based on ¹⁴C dating, 1964)

This fairly highly developed civilization (primarily urban) was in about 80 different locations spread over a vast area ca. 850,000 sq.km. in the plains along the course of the Indus (Sindhu) river and its five tributaries, extending from the foot of Simla hills in the north to a location west of Karachi (now in Pakistan) near the Arabian sea. In course of time this civilization spread to

Fig. 2. Potteries from Kulli and Zhob (pre-Harappan) : (a) Typical Kulli wares. (b) Typical Zhob wares.

other adjoining regions to the west, east and the south, viz., regions to the west of the Indus river, western Uttar Pradesh, Rajasthan (Bikaner district) and Gujarat. Further migrations presumably took place after several of the Indus Valley sites including the two important cities of Mahenjo-daro and Harappa were devastated by natural calamities and/or by a tribe of barbarian invaders from the west, when the Indus Valley people migrated as refugees to various other parts of the Indian sub-continent where they settled and continued with their life-style and practices. The various pre-historic sites (pre-Harappan, Harappan and post-Harappan) are located in parts of present Pakistan and many regions of India, in Baluchistan, and neighbouring parts of Sind province, Punjab, Haryana, Kashmir, Western Uttar Pradesh, Northern Rajasthan, several locations in Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Bihar, West Bengal, Orissa, Assam, Karnataka, Andhra Pradesh, Tamil Nadu and Kerala. The excavated objects from most of these sites include among others glazed coloured potteries, porcelain objects, metallic objects of gold, silver, copper, lead, and alloys like bronze (copper-tin), copper-arsenic alloy, and electrum (gold-silver). The Indus Valley Civilization was the largest and most developed of the world's three old civilizations, the other two being of Mesopotamia (Sumerian Civilization) and the Nile Valley in Egypt.

The Indus Valley people acquired considerable skill in making use of a wide range of processes which in-

involved chemical operations and techniques that laid the foundation of chemical technology in ancient pre-historic India. Articles excavated from Mahenjo-daro and Harappa include fired bricks of specific dimensions, glazed painted and coloured potteries (Fig 3) and porcelain objects such as vessels, jars, water-pots, terracotta objects, jewellery of metals with or without inlaid semi-precious stones, metallic objects like utensils, mirrors, vessels, etc., and metallic weapons and implements like choppers, daggers,

Fig. 3. Potteries from Harappa

spears, arrow-heads, etc. Incidentally, the art of brick and pottery making improved significantly in the following ages. Excavations at Taxila (ca. 6th century B.C. to 4th century A.D.) and at Bangarh in the Dinajpur district of West Bengal have yielded burnt decorative bricks and potteries of much superior quality and finish of the Sunga and the Kushana periods (ca. 2nd century B.C. to 2nd century A.D.) and of the Gupta period (ca. 3th-5th century A.D.). Terracotta figurines of ca. 2nd century B.C. to 6th century A.D. have been excavated from Boral (near Kolkata) and Tilpi in the South 24-Parganas and

Chandraketugarh in the North 24-parganas of West Bengal. Potteries from Arikamedu in Tamil Nadu belong to *ca.* 1st century A.D.

Chemical analysis of the ceramic materials excavated at Mahenjo-daro indicate high silica content (50–90%) with lime, magnesia, soda, alumina and iron oxide as the other constituents. Several of these also contain copper oxide, manganese oxide, etc., which were used to impart desired colours, viz., bluish-green (CuO), red (Cu_2O), yellowish-brown (Fe_2O_3), deep chocolate and black (due to Mn_3O_4 , MnO_2); for the red colour due to Cu_2O a reducing atmosphere was obviously maintained during the firing process. According to E. J. H. MacKay, an authority on Indus Valley Civilization, "The glazed pottery objects found at Mahenjo-daro represent the earliest such specimen in the world equal in finish to any glazed ware of ancient Mesopotamia of much later date and these are beyond all doubt the handiworks of potters who were well-acquainted with the process and able to carry it to a high degree of perfection." It is significant to mention here that in Egypt the practice of glazing potteries possibly started at a later date and in Mesopotamia the art appeared around 1000 B.C.

Slabs of glass-like substances of very high silica content (SiO_2 , 85–88%) with oxides of aluminium (Al_2O_3 , 3–4%), iron (Fe_2O_3 , 1.8–2%), copper (CuO , 0.5–1%), lime (CaO , 1.2%), alkalis ($\text{Na}_2\text{O} + \text{K}_2\text{O}$, 5–5.6%) have been found at Mahenjo-daro and Harappa. This material was presumably used for glazing the potteries. Apart from quartz as the body material for fine potteries, *steatite* (a variety of *talca* similar to *soapstone*) was also used. But this has not been found among the articles excavated from the ancient Nile Valley sites in Egypt. *Faience* is another fine ceramic material with quartz (pure natural silica, SiO_2) as the main constituent, which has been found at Mahenjo-daro and Harappa.

The finds of the Indus Valley sites further prove that the metal workers of that time were also very skillful and they possessed a good deal of knowledge on metal extraction from ores and in metal working for making various useful objects. They possibly had some knowledge in purification of the metals extracted from ores for use in specific purposes. Uses of the metals gold, silver, copper, lead and tin were known to them; tin was used as its alloy with copper, i.e., *bronze*, which was used extensively. Both copper and bronze were largely used for

domestic utensils, mirrors and other cosmetic objects, and bronze for various articles like chisels, axe-heads, daggers, knives, lance-heads, arrow-heads, sickles, etc., and bronze was preferred for making such objects because of its hardness (as compared to copper) and suitability in making tools and objects with sharp edges which is not damaged even after repeated use. For such tools and implements with sharp edges bronze with a fairly high tin content (*ca.* 10%) was required and since copper ores do not contain tin, a mixture of copper and tin ores in suitable proportions was obviously used in the smelting process to obtain bronze of the desired quality. The copper-arsenic alloys were presumably obtained by smelting of arsenical copper pyrites that occurs in nature. These alloys with arsenic content of *ca.* 2–4.5% were used as a substitute for inferior quality bronze with a much lower tin content than the bronze used in making tools and implements mentioned above. Analysis of several such copper and bronze objects has indicated the presence of *ca.* 1% nickel which suggests that the copper ores used had some nickel which is known to be true of the copper ores of Rajasthan and of many other regions of the world. Use of gold was mostly confined to jewellery, while silver was used for jewellery and for making ornamental vessels and articles for decorative use. Analysis of a silver sample from Mahenjo-daro indicated silver, 94.5%, with copper (3.7%) and lead (0.4%) as the major impurities. Articles made of a gold-silver alloy (*electrum*) have also been found at Mahenjo-daro and Harappa.

A large number of rocks, ores and minerals were known to the Indus Valley people who used these for various purposes. These were *Lapis Lazuli* (a blue coloured ultramarine, a silicate mineral) much valued as a semi-precious stone, *Turquoise*, *Carnelian*, *Onyx*, *Rock crystal*, *Gypsum*, *Alabaster*, *Soapstone*, *Limestone*, *Red-ochre*, *Haematite*, *Amethyst*, *Slate*, *Agate*, *Jasper*, *Bitumen*, *Steatite*, *Jade*, *Lollingite*, *Arsenical pyrites*, *Galena*, etc. Many of these materials were used as beads and pendants for ornaments; *Lollingite* and *Leucopyrite* (arsenical pyrites) were used to make *white arsenic* (arsenious oxide, As_2O_3) and arsenic. *Cerussite* and *Cinnabar* were used in cosmetic and some medicinal preparations. *White lead* ($2\text{PbCO}_3 \cdot \text{Pb}(\text{OH})_2$) was used as eye-salves, hair-washes and plaster, *Galena* was used for eye-salves and paints. Mortars were made of *Lime + Sand + Gypsum*, and

Gypsum was preferred for white plasters and as an additive in making white potteries.

The Indus Valley people knew the art of dyeing their cotton cloth with the red colouring matter obtained as extract from madder root, which is now known to be *alizarin* (now made synthetically); cultivation of madder for extracting the colour started in France only in the 18th century A.D. The Indus Valley people were also familiar with the blue dye indigo obtained from indigo plants. The Indus Valley people knew about these natural dyes and their use some 4000 years before the Europeans.

The Vedic Period (Aryan Civilization) (ca. 1500-600 B.C.)

After the decline of the Indus Valley Civilization, due to natural calamities and/or Aryan invasion, the next phase of importance is the Aryan Civilization, commonly referred to as the Vedic Period, being the period of composition of the *Vedas* (pronounced as *Bedas*), the religious texts of the Aryans but which deal with many aspects of the life and activities of the people of that time. The Aryans who migrated into India (from outside the Indian territory) initially settled in the north-western regions of India and gradually spread towards the east along the Gangetic plane. The Vedic Period represents the glorious period of the Aryan Civilization, with much intellectual developments.

In the *Rigveda*, oldest (ca. 1500-1400 B.C.) of the four *Vedas* compiled by the Aryans, we find mention of the metals gold (*harita*), silver (*rajata*), copper (*lohita*) and bronze (*kamsyaka*) and of objects made thereof. There is mention of large cooking vessels made of bronze for cooking of meat, but there is scanty mention of potteries in this and the other Vedic treatises. Mention of metallic vessels, tools and armour made mainly of bronze, and of gold and silver ornaments afford evidence of knowledge and skill of the Aryans in metal extraction and metal-working. In the *Yajurveda* of a later period (ca. 1200-1100 B.C.) we also find mention of iron (*krishna-yasa*) lead (*sisa*) and tin (*trappu*) among the metals. While excavations at southern Baluchistan have yielded specimens of iron implements (ca. 1500 B.C.) belonging to the post-Harappan and pre-Aryan period (ca. 1800-1500 B.C.), fairly large scale use of iron in India came at a later period (ca. 1000 B.C.) and there is definite mention of iron (*krishna-yasa* i.e., black metal) in the *Brahmanas*

and the *Upanisads* which are of a later period (ca. 800-500 B.C.). Various objects made of iron have been obtained by archaeological excavations at sites which date back to ca. 1000 B.C. From all the evidences it follows that iron smelting operations were common in India since at least 1000 B.C., and in the next four to five centuries the Indian iron and steel objects earned the admiration of the western world as well as the neighbouring countries.

There is scanty mention in the *Rigveda* about potteries for use as vessels for various household purposes. There is also mention of *leather* making from raw hides involving *tanning* process. The Aryans knew the art of *fermentation* and there is plentiful mention of various fermented drinks (*Soma*, *Madhu*, *Sura*) in the *Rigveda*. *Soma* was made from juice of the stems of Soma plant by fermentation, while *Sura* was made from barley by brewing and was possibly like the present-day beer. A common item of diet of the Aryans was *curd* (fermented milk) and they knew the process of making curd by appropriate fermentation from milk. The Aryans were also familiar with the art of *dyeing* and used to dye their clothes (mostly woolen) with various natural colouring matters of vegetable and plant origin including madder (*manjetthi*) and *neela* (*indigo*). Alchemical practices were also developed by the Aryans. In the *Atharvaveda* there is mention of various chemical preparations made from metals (gold, copper, lead, etc.) and those extracted from plants and vegetables for the treatment of diseases, for preventing hair loss and promoting hair growth, brightening complexion and for prolonging life. They had recognition of worms as causes of many diseases and there are descriptions of these worms. The *Atharvaveda* is rich in anatomical nomenclature. There is mention of diseases like fever, dysentery, jaundice, tuberculosis, ulcers, convulsion, menstrual disorder, etc., and their treatments, and surgical procedures for boils, wounds, fractures, amputation and artificial limb, abortion, cesarean child delivery, and use of *reed* as catheter for urinary tract.

Some plant products for curing diseases are also mentioned in the *Yajurveda* (the third of the four *Veda*). Thus, both Ayurveda and alchemy of later periods had their origin in the Vedic age particularly since the time of *Atharvaveda*. In the *Vedas* there are ample mention of several gems and precious stones, and we find mention of pearls and several gemstones in the epics *Ramayana* and

the *Mahabharata* (of ca. 600-400 B.C.) that these were used as jewels by the Kings and rich people.

Post-Vedic Period to Middle Ages

With the advancement of human civilization there was an urge for the pursuit of truth and for gaining knowledge as to the origin and nature of the universe. This led to many speculative views by Indian Philosophers which have the characteristics of scientific hypotheses. In this connection the views of the *Samkhya* and *Nyaya-Vaiseshika* systems (ca. 8th-5th century B.C.) need special mention. The orthodox systems of the Hindu Philosophies like the *Samkhya* the *Vaiseshika*, the *Nyaya* and *Yoga* and the *Chhandyoga Upanisad* are valuable source of information on the concept of creation of the universe and the origin and nature of matter. In terms of their origin, as per some authoritative views, the *Samkhya* is the older (ca. 800 B.C.) followed by the *Vaiseshika* (pre-Buddhist period), *Nyaya* (ca. 5th century B.C.) and the *Yoga* (ca. 150 B.C.). In some of the ancient philosophical treatises such as the *Chhandogy Upanishad* there are views having an analogy with the *Big Bang Theory* and the concept of the *Expanding Universe*. The *Samkhya* view on the origin of the universe, as proposed by Kapila (a propounder of the Sankhya Philosophy, ca. 6th century B.C.) (Patanjali, ca. 2nd century B.C., expressed similar views in his *Yoga* system) is broadly based on the principles of transformation and conservation of matter and energy. According to this, the universe evolved out of two cosmic forces, viz., *Purusa* (male) and *Prakriti* (female). In this we also find the theory of *Five Elements*, viz., *kshiti*, *ap*, *teja*, *vayu* and *akasa* (i.e., earth, water, fire/energy, air and "ether" respectively) which are the constituents of all matter. Similar views were expressed by the Chinese and the Greek philosophers later during the 5th century B.C. Greek philosopher Empedocles proposed the theory of *Four Elements* (earth, air, water and fire). According to Kapila, these 'elements' are composed of *paramanus* which are again composed of *tanmatras* (cf. 'attributes' of Aristotle, 4th century A.D.). Difference in properties of elements of the same *bhuta* class arises from difference in groupings of *tanmatras* in the *paramanus*. It is perhaps reasonable to consider this concept of elements of the ancient philosophers as representing the different states of matter (solid, liquid and gaseous), energy and

"ether". The concept of these "elements" combining in different proportions forming all the matter has a remote analogy with the scientific concept of compound formation by combination of elements, although the concept of "elements" of the above mentioned ancient wise men has no scientific validity. It is of interest also to note in this connection that Kanada a propounder of the *Vaiseshika* system (ca. 6th century B.C.) made a remarkable statement that light and heat are different forms of the same entity, viz., *teja* (energy) and further said that *akasa* (ether) is the universal medium in which corpuscles of light and heat move, and sound travels in the medium of *vayu* (air). He propounded the theory of four elements, (*Bhutas*) (*kshiti*, *ap*, *teja* and *vayu*) as components of matter.

A clearer idea that all matter is made up of minute and indestructible particles, *paramanu* (compare the Daltonian concept, 1801-1803 A.D. of *atom*) originated with the ancient Hindu philosophers. Kanada, the propounder of the *Vaiseshika* system of Indian philosophy, proposed the *atomic theory* of matter in ca. 6th century B.C. which has close resemblance with the views expressed by the Greek philosopher Democritus (460-370 B.C.). Kanada visualized the minutest particle of matter (*paramanu*) as indivisible, indestructible with inherent tendency to combine (hence do not exist in the free state) and are spherical in shape. Varahamihira visualized (ca. 550 A.D.) for the atom a diameter of the order of 10^{-6} cm in the modern scale which as we know now is too high (the actual value is of the order of 10^{-8} cm). His estimate was based on the phenomenon of scattering of light by suspended particles in air that make sunlight entering a dark room through a small hole visible to the naked eye and he made calculations considering the suspended particles in the air as *paramanus* which is of course not true. The ancient Indian philosophers also visualized some kind of force that leads to combination of atoms forming molecules (*anu*): they were also familiar with the classification of matter as *elements*, *compounds* and *mixtures*, as also the three-dimensional spatial arrangement of atoms in molecules (this was developed further by Vachaspati Mishra, 840 A.D.) and there is definite mention of atoms remaining in close contact in a cubic arrangement. Such an arrangement is now well-known from many crystallographic studies. The ancient Indians had no access to even any crude method of structure determination and yet the predictions they

made intuitively were indeed remarkable. Indian philosophical works, particularly of the *Nyaya-Vaisesika* system, noted the close association of chemical change with heat.

According to Vatsayana (*ca.* 400 A.D.) chemical change occurs either with application of external heat or due to effect of internal heat. It was believed (Vignana-Bikshu) that heat generated in combustion of a fuel existed in the fuel in a latent form (*cf.*, “inflammability principle” of Geber, 8th century A.D., and Stahl’s *Phlogiston Theory*, 17th century A.D. and the modern concept of *Enthalpy* and *Free Energy*). Udayana (*ca.* 1000 A.D.) in his treatise *Kiranavali* proposed solar heat as the ultimate source of all heat required for all the chemical changes occurring in the world. In his views on chemical combination Kanada (*ca.* 6th century B.C.) visualized formation of *mono-bhautic*, *hetero-bhautic* and *poly-hetero-bhautic* compounds (*Mahabhutas*), which correspond to what we know as *homoatomic*, *heteroatomic* and *poly-heteroatomic* molecules. According to A. A. Macdonell (1931) “Historical evidence points to the Greeks being influenced by the Indians in their philosophical concepts on the nature of matter”. According to H. T. Colebrooke (1817) “Indians were teachers rather than learners in this instance”. According to H. H. Wilson (1887) “... that the Hindus derived any of their philosophical ideas from the Greeks seems very improbable, and if there is any borrowing in the case, the latter were most probably indebted to the former”. The Buddhist scholars also believed in the atomic constitution of matter and their views were almost borrowed from the *Vaisesika*.

The *atomic theory* and the views regarding *chemical combination* were developed further by the Jainas during the 1st century A.D. A very significant feature of the atomism of the Jainas relates to the *mechanism of chemical combination* and binding between atoms (in molecule formation). It was postulated that atoms combine when they have perceptibly opposite qualities, or when atoms of similar character differ widely in the intensity of their qualities (*cf.*, modern concept of formation of ionic compounds in combination between electropositive and electronegative elements, and the electronegativity concept of Linus Pauling, proposed in 1932, in the formation of

polar covalent heteroatomic molecules). A detailed presentation of the atomic theory and chemical combination is found in the *Tattvarthadhigama-sutra* of Umasvamin (Umasvati, *ca.* 1st century A.D.). The views of the Jainas on chemical combination bear formal resemblance to the *Dualistic Hypothesis* (1812 A.D.) of J. J. Berzelius.

The alchemical practices developed by the Aryans were further developed and systematized in the following ages, viz., the *Ayurvedic Period* (*ca.* 600 B.C.-800 A.D.) and further in the *Tantric Period* (*ca.* 700-1300 A.D.). Several treatises of the post-Vedic period are a vast storehouse of information on the status of chemistry, metallurgy and medicine in ancient and medieval India and some of these typical treatises and their contents are mentioned in the following sections.

The science of Ayurveda (the Indian system of medicine, the art for healing) had its origin in the Vedic period and the *Atharvaveda* mentions recipes for medicinal use which has been mentioned earlier. The three most notable treatises of the Ayurvedic period are the *Arthasashtra* of Kautilya, the *Charaka Samhita* and the *Susruta Samhita* the original texts of the last two were written by a Charaka (*ca.* 3rd century B.C.) and a Susruta (*ca.* 10th and B.C.) respectively and their redactions made by the physicians Dradhabela (*ca.* 4th century A.D.) and Nagarjuna (*ca.* 5th century A.D.) respectively. Another ancient Ayurvedic treatise is the less known *Bhela Samhita* (*ca.* 10th century B.C.).

There is considerable controversy as to the age of these two Samhitas of Charaka and Susruta, and even with regard to the identity of Charaka and Susruta who authored these treatises, as there are mentions of different persons of widely different periods bearing these names (*loc. cit.*). Indeed, there is a similar problem with Nagarjuna, Vagbhata and some others, to whom we shall have to refer in subsequent sections. Charaka is a class title of a school of physicians since Vedic times, and the personal title of a physician in the court of King Kanishka and possibly the title of many other physicians belonging to a particular school of medicine at different ages in ancient India. Both these extant *Samhitas* of Susruta and Charaka are erudite and exhaustive treatises incorporating the theoretical and practical knowledge of medicine and its contributory sciences such as chemistry.

The two extant Samhitas of Susruta and Charaka are a

rich source of information on the status of knowledge in chemistry and medical science in ancient India. In the Charaka Samhita which is surely of a latter period (original text) there is more scientific approach as is evident from emphasis on experiments and holding of seminars.

The Khalifas of Bagdad had much appreciation of the developments in Ayurveda and allied sciences in India. "....they sent scholars to India to study medicine and pharmacology. Besides, they engaged Hindu scholars to come to Bagdad and made them chief physicians of their hospitals and ordered them to translate from Sanskrit to Arabic books on medicine, pharmacology, toxicology, philosophy, astrology and other subjects". -E. C. Sachu (1910) in "Al-Biruni's India".

The Arabian scholar Al-Biruni (973-1043 A.D.) acquired knowledge of Indian medicine from the translated Charak Samhita (translated into Arabic in the 8th century A.D.); Susruta Samhita was translated into Arabic in the 9th century A.D. and in several European languages in the 19th century A.D.

The information that we get in these Samhitas are briefly summarised below.

Susruta Samhita :

Alkalis - Three types (*Mridu*, *Madhyama* and *Tikshna*, i.e., mild, medium and strong) and their preparations. The lime-soda process for making strong alkalis (from soda or potash) used centuries later in Europe is mentioned, using extract of alkaline earth (soda) or wood-ash (potash) and burnt conch shells (lime).

Making of fermented drinks from rice, fruits, etc., glass (its difference from *sphatika* (crystals) was recognised), neutralisation of alkalis by acids (organic), drugs from vegetables and plants.

External medicinal use of copper sulfate (*sasyaka*), ferrous sulfate (*kasisa*), alum (*saurastri*), red-ochre (*gairika*), realger (*manassila*), etc.

White arsenic (*phenasmabhasma*) and arsenic sulfide, orpiment (*haritala*) for use as poisons.

Metals are made suitable for medicinal use by forming their 'calces' by mixing with salts and roasting in air. But there is scanty mention of mercury compounds in medicine.

Bronze vessel for storing drinking water was recommended. The ultra-trace amount of copper that gets dissolved from the bronze in water due to salts and in contact with air disinfects the water and this was surely recognised by practical experience and observations.

Charaka Samhita :

Theory of five elements and clearer concept of elements, compounds and higher compounds, and mixtures (*cf.*, Samkhya view, *loc. cit.*).

Mention of metals : gold, silver, copper, lead, tin, iron, bronze and brass.

Glass (*kaca*) is mentioned, and there is mention of several minerals (such as copper pyrites (*makshika*)), rust of iron, and calces of metals in medicine.

Use of copper sulfate (*sasyaka*), ferrous sulfate (*kasisa*), realgar (*manassila*), orpiment (*haritala*), sulfur (*gandhaka*) in combination with vegetable products for external application in skin diseases.

There is mention of saltpetre (*sauvarchala*), sal ammoniac (i.e., ammonium chloride, *chulika lavana*), alum (*saurastri*), rock-salt (*saindhava lavana*), sea-salt (*samudra lavana*), vegetable salts (*audvida lavana*), black-salt (*vit lavana*), etc.

There is mention of several chemical operations including calcination, sublimation, distillation steam distillation, etc.

Mention of potash (*yavakshara*), soda (*sarjikakshara*), borax (*tankana*) as mild alkalis (*mridu kshara*).

Classification of alkalis as *mridu*, *madhyama* and *tikshna* (*mild*, *medium*, *strong*). Solution of soda or potash on being boiled with burnt conch shell or limestone (lime, CaO) forms medium alkali, and this solution on long boiling (concentration) forms strong alkali.

Uses of ashes of conch shell, coral, lapis-lazuli (*rajavarta*), calces of iron and copper, rust of iron and pyrites (*vimala*) as constituents of medicine administered as pills. Recipes for medicinal preparations by boiling thin sheets of gold, silver, iron with solutions of salts or alkalis.

Stibnite (antimony sulfide, *nilanjana*) as an ingredient of a collyrium. Fermented drinks (*asavas*) of 84 different varieties made from ingredients from 9 different plant and vegetable sources, preparation of almost anhydrous alcohol.

Two kinds of medicines -

(a) For longevity, vitality, health and memory (*ayushyani*).

(b) For curing diseases (*Bhaishajyani*).

An essential qualification of a physician is knowledge of *vesajavidya* (i.e., medicinal properties of vegetable and plant products).

Minerals like bitumen (*silajatu*), orpiment (*haritala*), stibnite (*nilanjana*) and their uses.

Samhita	Medicinal compositions		
	Plant products	Animal products	Metallic salts and minerals
Susruta	395	57	64
Charaka	341	177	64

Incidentally it is worth mentioning some of the valuable information in the field of medical science that we see in the two *Samhitas*.

Charaka Samhita :

Exhaustive mention of symptoms of diseases and treatments for diabetes, diphtheria, tuberculosis of lung, malignant growth, leprosy, gangrene, erysipelas, jaundice, epidemic diseases, paralysis, epilepsy, tetanus, insanity, poisonous snake bite, bites of animals and hydrophobia.

Mention of 8 branches of ayurveda (medical science) : Therapeutics, toxicology, psychiatry, pediatrics, diseases of ENT, virility and potency, medicines, tonics and dosages, surgery.

Susruta Samhita :

Surgery : Eight classes of surgical procedures and 42 surgical processes for the following and also pre- and post-operative treatments. Fractures, piles, fistula, sinuses, tumours, malignant growth, cataract and other ophthalmic operations, carbuncles, hernia, urinary stones, gall stones, intestinal perforations, protrusion of the viscera due to accidental injuries, amputation of limbs, tonsillitis, bone abscesses, abscesses of internal organs, head injuries with exudation of brain matter, obstetric operations, removal of foetus by craniotomic and other methods, congenital malformation of nose, ear and lips involving plastic surgery, etc. The plastic surgery was of much help to criminals whose nose and ears were chopped off as punishment in those days.

Surgical Instruments (of Steel, *Pancaloha*) :

101 blunt varieties, 20 sharp instruments, their shapes, dimensions and making, surgical dressings and diets (including special salt-free diets). Suturing materials : made of flax, hemp and bark fibres and animal hair. Cataract couching was well-established (not known to the Surgeons of ancient Greece and Arabia). Emphasis on practical training for proficiency in Surgery, and dissection of a dead body for knowledge in Anatomy and Physiology.

Indian medical knowledge and surgical practices influenced much those in Greece and Arabia :

“It was in surgery above all that the ancient Hindus excelled, the Greeks drew much of their knowledge from the Hindus” – D. Guthrie (History of Medicine, London, 1920).

“The outstanding feats of the ancient Indian surgery related to laparotomy, lithotomy and plastic operations” – A. Neuberger (Geschichte der Medizin, 2 vols., 1906-11, English Translation by E. Playfair, London, 1910-25).

“In surgery we find proof of the priority of the Indians to Hippocratic medicine. Indeed, operations are described in the Indian texts, such as that of canal fistula, which are not mentioned in the Hippocratic writings” – “A History of Medicine”, A. Castiglioni, Alfred, A. Knopf, Inc., 1947.

“The whole of plastic surgery in Europe had taken its fight when these cunning devices of Indian workmen became known to us. The transplanting of sensible skin flaps is also an entirely Indian method” – Dr. Hirsberg (Berlin, Germany), quoted in “A Short History of Aryan Medical Science”, B. Shihjee, Macmillan & Co., 1896.

An important and comprehensive Ayurvedic compilation of the 2nd or 4th century A.D. is the *Navanitaka*, based on information in the *Samhitas* of Susruta, Charaka and Bhela, and several other earlier treatises. Its style of presentation is similar to that of Charaka, but there is no acknowledgement. In this there is mention of *Yabakshara* (Potash) and *Sarjikakshara* (Soda) and several minerals including *sisanjana* (galena, PbS). There are detailed descriptions of various diseases and their treatment using mixed medicines having minerals, metal compounds, vegetable and plant products. Medicines for diseases of the skin, eye, heart and leprosy and erysipelas are mentioned. Various compositions for enema and suppositories (rectal and vaginal), eye-salves and collyrium are given, as also of hair-dyes for blackening of hair. There is mention of catheters for male and female urinary tract.

Kautilya (Vishnugupta also known as Chanakya) was the learned and famous Prime Minister of Emperor Chandra Gupta (321-298 B.C.) of the Maurya dynasty. His treatise *Arthasashtra* (ca. 4th century B.C.) is a vast source of information on the status of chemistry and other branches of science in ancient India of that time. But according to some authorities the *Arthasashtra* was a prod-

uct of *ca.* 3rd century A.D., not authored by the above mentioned Chanakya. In the *Arthasashtra* there is a comprehensive account of gemstones and semi-precious stones (*diamond, ruby, emerald, sapphire, pearls, lapis lazuli*, etc.), corals, ores and minerals of metals such as gold, silver, copper, mercury, tin, lead, iron. Large scale processes for the extraction of these metals from their ores, their further processing and working and the properties of these metals are mentioned in the *Arthasashtra*. There is elaborate mention of purification of ores prior to metallurgical operation for metal extraction. Use of charcoal is specifically mentioned for iron metallurgy as fuel (and naturally also as source of carbon monoxide for the reduction of the oxide to the metal). In this treatise there are descriptions of several alloys such as bronze (*Kamsyaka*), brass (*Pittala*) alloys of gold and silver and copper as are suitable for making coins, assaying of gold and silver alloys to check their purity to protect against cheating by goldsmiths, descriptions of amalgams (alloys of metals with mercury) and of solders (lead-tin alloys) for soldering. Qualifications of Superintendents (*Adhakshas*) of mines and of metals and their duties are prescribed in the *Arthasashtra*. Brass was made in India since *ca.* 500 B.C. by smelting powdered calamine (zinc ore) mixed with copper chips or granules and charcoal in a furnace. The same process was used by the Romans since the time of Augustus (20 B.C.-14 A.D.) and followed in Europe till the 19th century A.D. All the information in the *Arthasashtra* indicate that mining and metallurgy reached a fairly advanced state of development in those days. In the *Arthasashtra* there is mention of several salts (based on the sources) viz., *saindhava lavana* (rock salt), *samudra lavana* (sea salt) and salt made from saline soil as found in some localities. There is mention of organic acids (such as in curd, this is lactic acid) obtainable by the process of fermentation. There was a significant development of the knowledge and skill in fermentation technology and *Arthasashtra* contains details of preparation of a variety of alcoholic drinks from rice, flour, sugar, honey, juices of fruits (grapes, mango, etc.) with or without spices for desired taste and flavour of the drinks. Extraction of oil from oil seeds is also mentioned in the *Arthasashtra*.

Several different varieties of glass including coloured glasses for decorative and ornamental use are described

in the *Arthasashtra*. Excavations at various sites such as Taxila (now in Pakistan), Ujjain, Kopia in the terrai region of Uttar Pradesh (all since *ca.* 500 B.C.), Hastinapur (*ca.* 800 B.C.), Nasik (*ca.* 200 B.C.) and Nalanda (5th century A.D.), etc., have shown that many different varieties of glass (Figs. 4 and 5) including coloured glasses, were made on a large scale for various use in ancient India, such as making ornaments (bangles) vessels and decorative objects and use in ornaments as a substitute for natural gemstones, at least since *ca.* 800 B.C. However,

Fig. 4. Glass specimens from Taxila (*ca.* 5th century B.C.) and Arikamedu (*ca.* 1st century A.D.): (1) Ear-reel, (2)-(4) Seals, (5)-(6) Eye-beads, (7)-(8) Beads, (9) Fragment of a Finger Ring of Blue Glass, (10) Flask for keeping wine, (11) Articles made of Agate, (12) Glass Bowl (Arikamedu), (13) Bangle piece, (14) Spirally wound Glass Bangle piece, (15) Glass sample (Arikamedu), (16) Blue Glass Amulet.

Fig. 5. Glass Vessels (Taxila, *ca.* 5th century B.C.).

excavations at Maski in southern Deccan region points to the fact that glass-making started in India even earlier (*ca.* 1000 B.C.). Incidentally, there is mention of glass in the *Satapatha Brahmana* and in the epic *Mahabharata*. Even in ancient times, as is done now, colouring of glass was effected using appropriate metal salts or metal oxides in requisite proportions with the glass-forming ingredients (sand, lime, soda, etc.). Pliny in his *Natural History* (1st century A.D.) has referred to Indian glass as superior to all others in quality and are good substitutes for semi-precious stones for use in jewellery.

Incidentally, the Mesopotamians knew the art of glass making since *ca.* 2600 B.C., while the Egyptians acquired the skill around 2000 B.C. Art of making painted decorated glazed pottery was fairly well-developed in the post-Vedic period since *ca.* 500 B.C. as seen from excavated findings from various locations all over India (*loc. cit.*).

From the information in the *Arthashastra* we may conclude that there was considerable advancement in the knowledge of metals, their extraction on a large scale from ores, their working either singly or as alloys for making various useful objects, viz., utensils, weapons, various implements, coins and jewellery. The workers in those days were very skillful in this regard. There was much improvement in fermentation technology, dyeing techniques, glass-making and making ceramic objects of high quality. Detailed descriptions of a large variety of ores, minerals, semi-precious and precious gemstones, pearls, corals, etc., indicate a fairly advanced state of knowledge of these materials and their uses. For the purpose of dyeing, natural colouring matter from vegetables, plants and fruits were used.

Among the 64 *Kalas* (skills) mentioned in ancient literary treatises like *Vagbhat Purana*, *Dasakumaracharita Kamasutra*, *Sukranitisara*, etc., there is mention of the following :

(a) Metal extraction, alloys and their preparation, (b) Alkalis and their preparation, (c) Medicinal uses of metallic preparations and of vegetable and plant products, (d) Artificial gold making, (e) Glass-making and making of glass-wares, (f) Making of arms and implements of iron and other metals.

Those possessing such skills were held in high esteem in the society. Many articles of copper, bronze, brass and lead of *ca.* 500 B.C. to *ca.* 400 A.D. have been exca-

vated at Taxila. The copper objects mostly having 99.7% copper indicates use of superior quality ore and skill in metal purification. Bronze with a very high tin content (20–24%) was preferred for making cast objects because of easy fusibility of this alloy as compared to bronze of lower tin content. Coins and fancy goods made of the silver coloured copper-nickel alloy have been excavated as also jewellery of gold and silver with inlaid gemstones. *Solders* made of lead-tin alloy have been found in some of the copper and bronze vessels excavated at Taxila.

Further advances in metal were made in India in later periods. A historical object that gives an insight into the admirable workmanship of the Indian artisans of ancient period is the famous iron pillar of very large size near Qutab Minar at Mehrauli in Delhi. This was originally installed as a victory pillar at Mount Vishnupada (possibly near Mathura) early in the 4th century A.D., during the reign of King Chandravarman of Rajasthan, but was later (1050 A.D.) removed to its present site by the King Anangapala-II when he rebuilt Delhi. This 7.4 m high pillar has a diameter of 41.7 cm at the bottom and tapers to 30.8 cm at the top and about 51 cm of the pillar is below the ground level; its estimated weight is about 6 tonnes. It is made of pure wrought iron having 99.72% iron, 0.08% carbon, 0.034% copper, 0.032% nitrogen, 0.046% silicon, 0.114% phosphorus, and 0.006% sulfur with no manganese. Absence of manganese is significant; very low percentage of sulfur indicates use of a high grade ore and most likely use of charcoal (not coal) as fuel in the furnace. The significant percentage of phosphorus, very low sulfur and absence of manganese account for the high corrosion resistance of the pillar material (wrought iron), since the surface of the pillar is still smooth and rustless although it has remained exposed to the atmosphere for sixteen centuries. It is also possible that the surface of the pillar was deliberately given a protective coating of the magnetic oxide of iron (Fe_3O_4). This could have been achieved by painting the surface with a mixture of some salts followed by strongly heating and quenching by immersion in water or oil. Even a few centuries earlier from our present time production of such a gigantic pillar would not have been possible in any of the foundries of the world.

In his book “Economic Geology of India” (1881), Valentine Bal expressed his views on the iron pillar of

Delhi as follows :

“The famous iron pillar at the Kutab near Delhi indicates an amount of skill in the manipulation of large masses of wrought iron, which has been the marvel of all who have endeavoured to account for it. It is not many years since the production of such a pillar would have been an impossibility in the largest foundries of the world, and even now there are comparatively few where a similar mass of metal could be turned out.”

The iron pillar (*ca.* 4th century A.D.) at Dhar, ancient capital of Malwa, also needs mention. The original pillar (now remaining broken into three pieces) was nearly twice the height of the Delhi pillar with a weight of over 7 tonnes. There is another victory pillar of 14th century A.D. also made of wrought iron with a height of 3.9 m having a trident at the top in the courtyard of the Achaleswara temple in Mount Abu in Rajasthan. There are also very large beams of pure wrought iron in the Sun Temple at Konarak (Orissa) of the 9th century A.D. and Sri Jagannath Temple at Puri (Orissa) of the 12th century A.D. Composition of the metal of the iron beams of Konarak temple is similar to that of the material of the Delhi pillar.

Steel making started in India around 500 B.C.; in all probability the process used was like the modern cementation process which was used in Europe since the middle of the 18th century A.D. Varahamihira has given (*ca.* 550 A.D.) two processes for hardening of steel. One of this involves plunging of red-hot steel into a solution of the plantain-ash in whay (the solution will have potassium lactate) and keeping for 24 hours. Steel thus treated can be sharpened on the lathe. The other recipe involves making a paste of the gelatine from sheep's horn, dung of the pigeon and the excreta of the mouse with the juice of arka plant and applying this paste to the surface of the steel smeared with seosom oil and then strongly heating the object followed by sprinkling of water, or milk of the mare or of the camel or the goat, or clarified butter, or blood, or fat, or bile on the red-hot object. Because of presence of nitrogen-rich materials (organic matter) in this recipe one expects that in the process 'nitriding' of the steel took place which is a well known modern technology. Indian steel, because of its quality, was in much demand in those days in other countries. The famous Damascas blades (swords) were made of Indian steel. A

noble visitor to the court of the Persian King in the 5th century B.C. mentioned two remarkable swords made of Indian steel presented to him by the King and the Queen Mother. After his surrender to Alexander, King Porus presented many gifts including 30 lb of Steel. Fine steel implements were obviously used for the stone inscriptions in the Asoka Pillars since *ca.* 300 B.C., and as mentioned in the *Susruta Samhita (loc. cit.)* surgical instruments made of steel were in use during that time. Earlier bronze was mostly used for the purpose. In the treatises *Yuktikalpataru* (11th century A.D.) and *Sarangadhara Paddhati* (14th century A.D.) there are mentions of places in India, Ceylone and Nepal where swords of high quality were made using Indian steel. Iron articles excavated from the ancient sites at Taxila (4th century B.C. to 4th century A.D.), Tirunelveli (4th century B.C.) and Bangarh (in Dianjpur district of West Bengal, 4th century B.C.-5th century A.D.) are mostly household utensils, weapons, tools for carpenters and blacksmiths and agricultural implements.

Iron clamps of the famous temple at Bodh Gaya and iron slag found at the foundation of the *stupa* at the same place (3rd century B.C.) and the large number of iron beams and clamps of the Lingaraja Temple at Bhubaneswar (Orissa; 640 A.D.) are also significant finds.

The Chinese pilgrim Hiuen Tsang mentioned in his chronicle the extensive use of brass in India at the time of his visit (7th century A.D.). He mentioned a huge statue of Lord Buddha made of copper (height 24.4 m) and of an unfinished Vihara (convent) of brass built near Nalanda by the Emperor Harshavardhana (7th century A.D.). Another copper statue of Buddha (height 2.3 m, weight nearly one tonne) of *ca.* 5th Century A.D. (Fig. 6) was discovered in the ruins of a Buddhist monastery at Sultanganj near Bhagalpur in Bihar. This was found by an officer of the British East India Company who removed this piece of art to England and it is now housed in the Art Gallery at Birmingham, since 1864. A big size solid bolt of metallic copper (62.2 cm long, diameter 11.3 cm at the middle and 9.7 cm at the ends) exquisitely worked into shape was found (in 1881) near the Asoka Pillar at Rampurwa near the Nepal border. It is made of pure copper and is now in the Indian Museum at Kolkata. The bolt was possibly used for fixing the large stone capital of the Asoka Pillar to the body of the pillar. Copper objects excavated

from the Indus Valley sites generally have *ca.* 1% nickel. But the copper objects of later periods excavated from Taxila and other such places have a lower nickel content (0.1–0.4%).

Fig. 6. Copper Statue of Goutam Buddha (Sultanganj, *ca.* 5th century A.D.).

In India since ancient times copper, bronze and brass were used quite extensively for ornaments, utensils, mirrors and cosmetic objects, armours, tools and implements for various purposes. Many such uses were taken over by iron since *ca.* 5th century B.C. In a treatise *Arkaprakasha* (16th century A.D.) use of tin-plated copper vessels are recommended for carrying out distillation. Cooking vessels of tin-plated copper were much in use since the Mughal period (16th century A.D.) because of resistance of tin to corrosion by acidic foods and thereby avoiding copper poisoning as copper is fairly readily dissolved by organic acids. In *Ayeeni Akbari*, Abul Fazal of Emperor Akbar's court has mentioned tin-plated copper vessels were used for cooking the Emperor's food and for his other uses. An alloy of copper-lead-tin-zinc of blackish colour (known as *bideri*) was much in use during the Mughal period for making cups, vases, basins, etc., with inlaid decorations of gold and silver leaves on them. *Enamelling* i.e., fixing of glazed colours by firing of metal objects, particularly

of gold and silver, using appropriate enamelling composition, was much in use since the Mughal period (16th century A.D.).

It has been mentioned earlier that the Indus Valley people were familiar with the art of dyeing their clothes with the natural red colouring matter present in the extract of the roots of Madder plant. The Aryans of later period were also familiar with the art of dyeing with the colouring matter from Madder (*manjetthi*) and other natural colouring matter of vegetable origin such as indigo, Panini (*ca.* 5th century B.C.) has mentioned indigo, lac and red-ochre for dyeing clothes. In *Samyukta Nikaya* Buddha is said to have made mention of resin (*ranjana*), indigo (*nili*), lac (*laksha*), turmeric (*halidda*) and madder (*manjetthi*) for use as dyes. The *Vinaya* text of the Buddhists mentions six sources of dyes from the vegetables, plants and fruits. *Vrihata Samhita* of Varahamihira (6th century A.D.) mentions the use of alum, green vitriol and even cowdung as agents (*mordants*) that give fast colour on dyeing with madder and other such dyes; these serve to fix the colour which is not easily washed out.

There is evidence that ink made from lamp-black was in use in India since *ca.* 400 B.C. The ancient manuscripts, now preserved in many of the museums of the world, were written with such carbon black ink on palm leaf or birch-bark, as paper was not known in those days. In the *Rasaratnakara* of Siddha Nityanatha of the 13th century A.D. we find a recipe for making indelible black ink with lamp-black mixed with some vegetable and plant products. This marked the beginning of ink production on a large scale. The remains of the ancient cave paintings of Ajanta (200 B.C.–400 A.D.) and at other places suggest use of several colouring matter, mostly minerals, such as red-ochre (*dhaturationa*), orpiment (*haritala*), indigo (*nila*), lapis lazuli (*rajavarta*), cinnabar (*hingula*), red lead, lamp-black (*kajjali*), chalk (*khari mati*), yellow ocher (*gairika*), and jangal (*verdigris*, green coloured basic copper acetate, or possibly the naturally occurring green coloured mineral *malachite* which is a basic carbonate of copper), etc.

In the *Vrihat Samihita* of Varamamihira (6th century A.D.) there is detailed information on the preparation and uses of several fine chemicals like perfumes, scented

hair oils, hair dyes, etc. Perfumery is elaborately discussed in this treatise with recipes to make perfumes that imitate the scents of flowers of different varieties. Evidently, the knowledge of the chemical techniques for production of perfumes had reached an advanced state by that time. In this treatise several recipes are given of compounded (i.e., deliberately blended) perfumes of superior qualities. Sixteen essential ingredients for the preparation of a wide variety of perfumes are mentioned in this treatise. In this we also find mention of two cementing materials *Vajra-lepa* (stone cement) and *Vajra-samghata* (metal cement). The *vajra-lepa* was made of a mixture of several gummy plant products, gelatinous materials from animal body parts and natural resinous substances; this mixture when applied between two pieces of stone bind the pieces extremely firmly. *Vajra-samghata* was made by melting lead, bronze and brass in the ratio of 8 : 2 : 1 parts by weight; the molten mixture was poured for cementing metal pieces with its solidification. Descriptions of many different varieties of precious and semi-precious stones also appear in this *Vrihat Samhita*.

Much of the developments in chemistry in India in the Medieval Period derived its nourishment from the alchemists of India which are well documented in over two dozen treatises of the Tantric Period by different authors. The alchemical practices which reached a peak during the early stages of the Tantric Period had their origin much earlier. In the *Atharvaveda* (the last of the four *Vedas*, ca. 1100-1000 B.C.) we find mention of some practices and rituals of the Tantric cult. In several literary works of the 6th century A.D. we come across mention of chemical preparations that produce deep sleep on inhalation of its vapour and of those that serve as anaesthetic. Indeed, both Ayurveda and Alchemy had their origin in the *Atharvaved* (ca. 1100-1000 B.C.). Emergence of alchemy in Europe was in the 13th century A.D.

Alchemy had its origin in China (ca. 2nd century B.C.) from where it went Egypt and flourished there during 1st-7th century A.D. Arabians invaded Egypt in 640 A.D. and they acquired the knowledge from Egyptians in the 7th century A.D. and from there it passed on to Europe in the 13th century A.D. and flourished there for a few centuries till the emergence of modern chemistry in the 16th century A.D. through a phase of Iatrochemistry.

A very renowned alchemist of India, who was a Buddhist by religions, was Nagarjuna who belonged to the 8th or 9th century A.D. As mentioned by Al-Biruni (the

Arabian scholar, 973-1048 A.D.) this Nagarjuna was a native of a place near Somnath and belonged to a time well over a century before Al-Biruni. He was a renowned chemist and metallurgist of medieval India. He authored several treatises such as *Rasaratnakara*, *Arogyamanjari*, etc. These treatises of Nagarjuna and several others of later periods (ca. 12th-14th century A.D.) such as *Rasarnava*, *Rasendrachuramani*, *Rasaratnasamuchchaya*, *Rasaprakasasudhakara*, *Rasapradipa*, *Rasakaumudi*, etc., provide much valuable information on the knowledge of chemistry, metallurgy and medicine of the medieval period in India.

In the *Rasaratnaka* of Nagarjuna (ca. 8th-9th century A.D.) we find a detailed description of a number of chemical operations and transmutation processes for the conversion of baser metals into materials having the colour and lustre similar to that of gold. Several, such transmutations of copper, lead and silver are mentioned. There are also detailed descriptions of metallic preparations, a few being of mercury, of much medicinal use. The work on transmutation was like those of the alchemists of Europe in the middle ages (ca. 13th century A.D.) and like them the Indian alchemists had a firm belief in the possibility of transforming baser metals into gold; they also believed in the possibility of discovering an Elixir of Life (*Amrita*) that would cure all diseases and considerably prolong a man's life or even make man immortal; preparation of a gold-like material by roasting powdered calamine and copper with carbonaceous matter is described in this treatise. The material obtained was obviously brass (a copper-zinc alloy). There is also mention of preparation of some gold-like amalgams. Extraction of mercury from cinnabar, of copper from copper pyrites, and of zinc from calamine are mentioned in this treatise. This is the first mention of zinc extraction in any Indian treatise and in fact the earliest in the world. In Europe extraction of zinc from calamine was achieved only in the ca. 18th century A.D. Purification of mercury (*parada*) by distillation is mentioned in the *Rasaratnakara*. Preparation of mercury sulfide by heating a mixture of a gold amalgam (gold-mercury alloy), borax and sulfur in a closed vessel and collecting the red mercury sulfide as a sublimate is mentioned. It is stated that this is an elixir that "makes the body not liable to decay".

In India as in China, alchemical ideas evolved around a male-female symbolism in which mercury was consi-

dered as male (symbolically the seminal essence of Lord Shiva, a God of Hindu mythology) and sulfur as female (symbolically the menstrual flux of Shiva's consort Goddess Parvati). Hence, a combination of the two forming mercury sulfide is an *Amrita* that helps preserving youthful vitality, promote health and long life. Similar views were held by Chinese alchemists. Preparation of black mercury sulfide (*kajjali*) is also mentioned, which is mentioned later by Chakrapani also (*loc. cit.*). Other important information in the *Rasaratnakar* are the following :

(a) Purification of important ores and minerals.

(b) Purification of metals such as mercury, copper, silver and gold.

(c) Dissolution of pearls and gemstones by digestion with vegetable acids.

(d) "Killing" of metals (formation of oxides/sulfides).

(e) "Killing" of diamond (*Vajram*), i.e., its conversion to a fine powder.

(f) "Liquifaction" of mica (*avhra*).

(g) A list of several *Yantrams* (apparatus) for use in chemical laboratory (mostly borrowed from an earlier treatise *Rasendramangala*) and descriptions of most of them. The recommendation for purification of mercury by distillation has been mentioned earlier. For purification of copper the recommended process involved melting copper with some plant products and in this respect it resembles the "poling" process developed a few centuries later in Europe. "Killing" of diamond involved a thermal operation to convert it into a fine ash achieved by strongly heating the diamond and quenching the hot diamond by throwing it into mercury. "Liquifaction" of mica involves melting the mica with soda and borax forming a clear melt (this transforms mica into acid soluble form). This is like the modern method of fusing refractory silicates with fusion mixture (sodium carbonate + potassium carbonate) to convert the silicate into an acid soluble form.

More elaborate descriptions of the *yantrams* (Fig. 7) are in the *Rasarnava* (12th century A.D.) and particularly in the *Rasaratnasamuchchaya* (14th century A.D.) of later periods. Purification of gold and silver by alloying with lead followed by cupellation, as in modern practice, is mentioned in the *Rasaratnakara*. During the Tantric Period (*ca.* 700-1300 A.D.) we notice a phase of transi-

tion (particularly during 900-1100 A.D.) in the system of Indian medicine with regard to the nature and composition of substances used in making the medicines. Hitherto herbs and vegetable and plant products were largely used as constituents of medicinal preparations with a few naturally occurring minerals and metallic preparations made from metals. Vagbhata (*ca.* 9th century A.D.) prescribed mostly minerals and natural salts along with herbal medicinal products. Vagbhata, a Buddhist by religion, was held in high esteem as an authority in medicine next to Charaka and Susruta. Vagbhata (author of *Astangahridaya*) prescribed a recipe of a mixture of blue vitriol, green vitriol, red-ochre, realgar and orpiment for external use in the treatment of sores. But he made a casual mention of use of mercury in one preparation of a collyrium which was made of an amalgam of lead, antimony sulfide and camphor. Hence, not much was known as to the properties and uses of mercury compounds at that time. But some metallic preparations of gold, silver, copper, iron, antimony, tin and lead were described and recommended for medicinal use. This demonstrates an advanced state of

Fig. 7. Some of the 30 Laboratory apparatus (*Yantrams*) for specific chemical operations (*Rasaratnasamuchchaya*, 14th century A.D.) and several of these are also to be found in some earlier treatises, viz., *Rasaratnakara*, and *Rasendramangala*. Names of the *Yantrams* : (a) Svedani, (b) Patana, (c) Adhaspatana, (d) Musa, (e) Dheki, (f) Tirjakpatana, (g) Dola, (h) Vidyadhara, (i) Dhupa, (j) Baluka/Lavana (Sand/Salt bath), (k) Kosthi.

knowledge on the properties of metal compounds and their preparations for medicinal use. As in the *Susruta Samhita*, Vagbhata also mentioned making of caustic alkali from mild alkali by treatment with lime (*loc. cit.*).

It is quite certain that there was increasing use of metallic preparations in medicines since Vagbhata's time and particularly since 10th century A.D. every medical treatise emphatically recommended the use of compounds of metals, mostly those made in the laboratory. This led to emergence of a system of Ayurveda known as *rasachikitsa*. Many medicinal preparations containing compounds of mercury, copper, iron, etc., particularly the sulfides, were mentioned in different treatises of this period written by Vrinda (*Siddhayoga*, ca. 1000 A.D.), Chakrapani Datta (*Chakrasamgraha*, ca. 1050 A.D.) and others. Both Vrinda and Chakrapani deserve particular credit for the wide medicinal use of mercury sulfide.

In *Siddhayoga* mercury was mentioned as a constituent of a medicine to be applied externally for killing lice, and the use of copper compounds in the preparation of a collyrium (Chakrapani also mentioned an identical preparation). Mercury sulfide was the main ingredient of a preparation recommended by Vrinda to be administered with clarified butter and honey as medicine; this medicinal preparation was named *rasamrita churnam* (made with mercury sulfide obtained by rubbing in a mortar mercury and sulfur in proper proportions). In another preparation (*parpatitamram*) the ingredients were mercury sulfide and copper sulfide, obtained by roasting, copper, sulfur, pyrites and mercury in a closed vessel. Chakrapani described a number of metallic preparations, one being *rasamrita* which was made of mercury sulfide (black variety, *kajjali/rasaparpati*).

Chakrapani also mentioned preparation of copper sulfide by heating copper chips with sulfur in proper proportions in a covered vessel and its use in medicine with other drugs. He also mentioned use of rust of iron (hydrated ferric oxide) and "killed" silver (silver sulfide) in medicines. Both Vrinda and Chakrapani mentioned preparation of a collyrium using "killed" copper (copper oxide), blue vitriol, rock-salt and several vegetable products, all mixed thoroughly. Chakrapani named this *Nagarjuna Varti* in honour of the renowned alchemist Nagarjuna (ca. 8th-9th century A.D.). Chakrapani also

mentioned preparation of a soap (potassium soap) by boiling mustard oil with a caustic alkali that he made as per earlier recipe by boiling a solution of potash (from wood-ash) with lime (CaO). This appears to be the first mention of soap making in any ancient Indian treatise; prior to this wood-ash, sajimati and extracts of some berries were used for cleansing.

Rasahridaya (ca. 11th century A.D.) of Govinda Bhagbhat mentioned a *vida* for "killing" metals, properties of metals and of several minerals, various salts including sal-ammoniac (*chulika lavana*) and the three alkaline substances, potash, soda and borax, as in many other earlier treatises.

In the *Rasarnava* of the 12th century A.D. (author anonymous) we first find mention of colours imparted to flame by some metallic compounds. As in earlier treatises there is mention of extraction of copper from pyrites, zinc from calamine and making brass from calamine and copper, and of another gold-like alloy of copper-zinc-lead. Making of metallic copper from blue vitriol is also described in the *Rasarnava*. It also mentions recipes for making *vida* for "killing" of gold and other metals. The *vida* is a paste made of some metal salts, some minerals, some organic matter including animal urine which is applied to the metal surface and then strongly heated whereby the metal gets "killed". The process obviously transforms the metal into its oxide or sulfide or even a salt. Two of the recipes for *vida* mentioned in the *Rasarnava* are the following :

(a) Green vitriol, rock-salt, pyrites, stibnite, powdered spices (black pepper, long pepper and dry ginger), juice of some plants (names given) all mixed together.

(b) Sulfur, orpiment, sea-salt, sal-ammoniac, borax digested with plant ashes and urines.

There are two other similar recipes of *vida* specifically mentioned for "killing" of gold and mercury.

A recommended process for purification of mercury involved rubbing the mercury with the juice of 21 plants (names given) followed by distillation carried out 7 times. Another involved making an amalgam with copper followed by distillation and collecting the pure mercury as distillate; the tin and lead impurities and the copper are left behind. In the *Rasarnava* the following almost correct order of corrosion resistance of metals is given :

gold > silver > copper > iron > tin > lead. As in several earlier treatises it mentions of the three alkaline substances, soda, potash and borax. There is mention, of various *yantrams* (apparatus) as in some other treatises.

Rasarnava mentions distillation of alum (*saurashtri*) and collecting its “essence” as distillate. This is of course sulfuric acid and this appears to be the first mention of a mineral acid in an old Indian treatise. The same process is mentioned in at least two other treatises viz., *Rasaprakasasudhakara* (13th century A.D.) and *Rasaratnasamuchchaya* (14th century A.D.); this latter also mentions of “essence” of green vitriol (*kasisa*) obtained by its distillation, this “essence” is also sulfuric acid. This method of making sulfuric acid was used in Europe since ca. 16th century A.D. till Wood introduced (in 1740) the process of burning sulfur with nitre in a large glass vessel in presence of water, which was the precursor of the lead chamber process introduced in the year 1746. In the *Dhatukriya* (17th century A.D.) this acid has been referred to as *Dahajala* (burning water) because it causes severe skin burn. Another mineral acid which is a universal solvent for metals and conch-shell is mentioned in several treatises of the 16th century A.D., viz., *Rasakaumudi* of Madhava, *Rasapradipa*, and *Rasaratnapradipa* and *Bhaishajyaratnavali* of Govindadasa, etc. The recipes given involved distilling a mixture of alum, green vitriol, sal-ammoniac and/or rock-salt, sea-salt, saltpetre and borax and collecting the “essence” as a distillate. It has been named by different authors as *Samkhadravaka* (solvent for conch-shell) and *Mahadravaka* (universal solvent, because it also dissolves all metals). The method of preparation obviously suggests that this is *aqua regia* (a mixture of hydrochloric and nitric acids). Somadeva’s *Rasendrachuramani* (12th-13th century A.D.) is another treatise of the Tantric Period in which extraction of antimony from the mineral stibnite (*nilanjana/srotanjana-* or *anjana*) is described for the first time. The method being heating the mineral strongly with metallic iron. In Europe antimony was not made before 1492 (*loc. cit.*). Incidentally, in ancient India since very early periods this mineral was used as a cosmetic for blackening eye-brows. Preparation of calomel (*svetavasma / karpurarasa*) and its medicinal uses are mentioned in several treatises of the 13th-16th century A.D. These are *Rasaprakasasudhakara* (Yasodhara, 13th

century A.D.), *Rasachintamani* (Madanantadeva, 13th century A.D.), *Rasapradipa* (16th century A.D.) and *Bhavaprakash* (Bhavamishra, 16th century A.D.). All these describe preparation of calomel by very similar methods (heating a mixture of common salt, alum, borax, mercury and some vegetable products (with red-ocher, and clay in some recipes) in a closed vessel and collecting the calomel as a white sublimate). Red-ocher (Fe_2O_3) is now known to catalyse oxidation of the liberated HCl to Cl_2 which facilitated the reaction. The first treatise mentions the use of calomel (Hg_2Cl_2) as an aphrodisiac and in treatment of leprosy, while the last two treatises mention its use in the treatment of syphilis (*phiringaroga*, so called as this was brought to India by the Portuguese sailors in the 16th century).

In the *Rasakalpa* there is mention of the six known metals and some alloys as in the earlier treatises. In this, extraction of copper from pyrites is said to be carried out by digesting the powdered mineral 100 times with the juice of plaitain leaves, then steeped for three days in oil, clarified butter and honey, and then heated strongly in a pot yielding the “essence” of *makshika* (which is metallic copper).

In *Rasakalpa* there is mention of minerals of three classes, viz., *maharasas*, *rasas* and *uparasas* and examples of each class are given, but what was the rational basis of this classification is not clear. Of the various minerals mentioned in this treatise one is *kankustha* (cassiterite, tinstone, a common ore of tin).

In this treatise there is mention of four kinds of sulfur, viz., white, yellow, red and black : these are obviously different allotropic forms of sulfur. It mentions a recipe for “killing” gold and other metals, being a mixture of sal-ammoniac (*chulika lavana*), sulfur, ginger, etc., digested 100 times with cow’s urine.... The metal is painted with this *vida* (a paste) and heated strongly when the metal gets “killed” (the metal changes into an oxide, sulfide, etc.). Extraction of a “tin-like essence” (zinc) from calamine is also mentioned in this treatise (*Rasakalpa*).

In the Iatrochemical period (ca. 14th-16th century A.D.) we notice a change in attitude from the irrational alchemical objectives to a more rational approach in the search for and applications of metallic salts and chemicals in medicine (*cf.*, Europe in the 15th century A.D.).

Rasaratnasamuchchaya (ca. 14 century A.D., Vegbhata, Jr.) is a typical treatise of the Iatrochemical Period. It mentions mica of three different types and many minerals including *kamkustha* (cassiterite) and many gemstones, and methods of extraction of several metals (Cu, Zn, Sb, Hg), making white arsenic from arsenic sulfide minerals, etc. This also deals with the well-tried mercurials and minerals as are useful in treatment of diseases. Distillation of alum and green vitriol forming their essences (obviously sulfuric acid) is also described in this treatise. Several thermal processes for “killing” diamond (reducing to fine powder) and processes for “killing” metals (conversion to oxide, sulfide and even salts) are also described. There is a full description of an ideal chemical laboratory and elaborate mention of various types of *yantrams* (apparatus) for use in performing chemical operations (Fig. 7). There are the following recommendations about laboratory and laboratory workers in the *Rasaratnasamuchchaya* which are worth noting :

“The laboratory is to be erected in a region which abounds in medicinal plants and wells and well furnished with various apparatus.”

“Those who are truthful, free from temptations, self-controlled, live on proper diet and are believer in God are to be engaged in performing chemical operations.”

“Those who are not deceitful and are well-versed in the knowledge of drugs and plants and the language of many countries should be employed.”

Rasendrasarasangraha of Gopalakrishna (14th century A.D.) stresses on efficacy of metallic preparations in medicine and gives less importance to herbal drugs.

Detailed preparations of some mineral acids are given in several treatises of the 16th century A.D., viz., *Rasakaumudi* of Madhava, *Rasapradipa* and *Bhaishajyaratnavali* of Govindadasa, as has been mentioned before. Regular use of mineral acids in technical operations and in the refining of gold and silver was in vogue during the reign of the Mughal Emperor Akbar (16th century A.D.). The art of recovery of gold from wastes in jewellery making involved chemical operations like treatment with acids, alloying with lead followed by cupellation, etc., which were well-known to Indians since quite early days and surely from pre-Mughal period.

Arkaprakasha of Ravana (ca. 16th century A.D.) which

is mainly a treatise on the preparation of medicinal tinctures and essences, uses of essential oils and opium in medicine, etc., also needs mention. As mentioned earlier, there is recommendation in this treatise for use of tin-plated copper vessels for distillation. It also mentions use of the product of treatment of mercury with *sankhadravaka* (*aqua regia*, HCl + HNO₃) in the treatment of syphilis. The product of the said reaction with excess mercury was obviously calomel (Hg₂Cl₂).

Another development was manufacture of paper which started in India ca. 1000 A.D., the technology of which was possibly imported from China through Nepal. Paper came into regular use on a fairly large scale since 14th century A.D. Mahaun (a Chinese visitor) came to Bengal in the year 1406 and spoke of a high quality smooth and glossy paper made in Bengal from the bark of a tree.

Mention has been made earlier on the knowledge and skill of the ancient Indians in making cosmetics and perfumes as documented in *Vrihat Samhita* of Varahamihira (ca. 6th century A.D.). In subsequent periods this industry made considerable progress in India and new techniques and compositions were developed. Texts dealing with perfumery and elegant methods of fragrance upkeep of the body were composed during this period.

Of these the *Gandhasara* of Gangadhara (11th-12th century A.D.) deserves mention. In this six processes for preparation of cosmetics and some 25 different types of fragrant water and of a number of fragrant aromatic substances are mentioned. The details throw ample light on the technical skill of the perfume makers who were well acquainted with the art of blending and curing, i.e., intensification of fragrance, of different perfumes. The *Gandhavada* written by an anonymous author in the 14th-15th century A.D. is another important treatise in perfumery of the medieval period. Imported substances like opium from China were incorporated into Ayurvedic pharmacology around 1500 A.D. Tinctures and essential oils came into use about the same time.

There is evidence that guns, cannons and gunpowder were in use in Bengal and other parts of India in the beginning of the 15th century A.D. At the beginning of the Mughal Period (early 16th century A.D.) gunpowder for use in guns and cannons became an article of warfare. *Sukraniti* of Sukracharya (16th century A.D.) gives a

description of how gunpowder is prepared using saltpetre, sulfur and charcoal mixed in different ratios for use in different types of guns and cannons. Guns and cannons of huge size excavated from various locations in Bengal and other parts of India, belonging to a period since ca. 1400 A.D. (mostly made of iron, and also brass and bronze) also demonstrate the high skill of metal workers of those days. A century or two earlier Indians acquired knowledge of pyrotechny from the Chinese. Use of fireworks during ceremonies and festivals became a common practice in different parts of India since ca. 1500 A.D. But several centuries earlier (ca. 6th century A.D.) we find mention in the literary work *Dasakumaracharita* by Dandi of *yogavartika* (magic-wick) and *yogachurna* (magic powder) of which the former had saltpetre as a constituent. The former produced light without fire, while inhalation of the latter produced deep sleep.

In the literary work *Vasavadatta* (6th century A.D.) there is mention of *Stambhanachurnam* an anaesthetic that paralyzes sensory and motor nerves. There are several other treatises of the Tantric and Iatrochemical Periods dealing with different aspects of knowledge in chemistry and its applications but hardly different from those in some of the representative treatises of this period which have already been mentioned in the preceding section.

It is of interest to note here that in all these treatises of ancient and medieval periods the processes described for extraction of metals from ores and minerals, purification of minerals and of the metals, “killing” of metals, diamonds, pearls, etc., involved mixing the materials with various organic matter like plant and vegetable products, butter, oil and even animal urine, excreta of birds and animals, etc., followed by heating. The organic matter presumably served the purpose of a reducing agent and also fuel and being mixed intimately ensured uniform heating throughout the mixture for the chemical changes to take place. Thus, for extraction of copper from pyrites (*makshika*) the following procedure is mentioned in the *Rasarnava* (also in the *Rasaratnakara* and *Rasaratnasamuchchaya*) :

“Makshika repeatedly soaked in honey, oil of *Ricinus communis*, urine of cow, clarified butter and the extract of the bulbony root of *Musa sapientum* and heated in a crucible yields an essence in the shape of tamram (copper).”

Obviously, the recipe would have worked even without cow’s urine. Varahamihira’s prescriptions for hardening of steel which have been mentioned earlier are also based on trial observations. Steel gets hardened even by strong heating and then quenching in water or oil and the use of bird or animal excreta is unnecessary, although their use may lead to which we now know of case hardening due to nitriding. Interestingly animal excreta and animal urine is mentioned in many of the recipes; not only so, in *Rasaratnasamuchchaya* the author has specifically prescribed that urines of elephant, she-buffalo, mare and ass are to be used. *Rasarnava* mentions that “*saurashtri* (alum) is to be macerated in the bile of the ox one hundred times and then its essence is extracted by distillation”. This is of no scientific basis, as alum itself on being strongly heated will decompose liberating SO_3 and, H_2O vapour and this on condensation will form H_2SO_4 (sulfuric acid). There are many such examples of procedures for extraction of metals from ores, purification of metals, etc., but no systematic attempt was made to understand the chemical changes involved and the essential conditions for the changes to occur to further rationalize the empirical knowledge. In the *Rasaratnasamuchchaya* the following process of “killing” diamond (*vajram*) is mentioned :

“*Vajram* is to be placed in a covered crucible, the inside of which has been coated with realgar, rubbed with the decoction of *kulattha* and the juice of *Artocarpusi akoocha* and roasted eight times in succession in the fire of dry cow-dung cake. It is then heated and thrown into *parada* (mercury) the vajram is thus killed and reduced to fine ashes.”

The same treatise mentions the following properties of diamond (which is unbelievable on the basis of current scientific knowledge) : “*Vajram* is a bestower of long life, a tonic, an allayer of the three derangements *vayu*, *pitta* (bile) and *kafa* (phlegm), a killer of all the ailments, a fixer of *parada* (mercury), a subduer of death – in short it is like *amrita* (nectar)”. *Rasaratmasamuchchaya* has described “killed” diamond for use in medicine, which is difficult to explain.

Thus despite much progress in empirical knowledge ancient Indian chemistry did not attain the state of rationality of a modern science. But we cannot ignore the fact that many of the developments in chemistry of use to man and which influenced the progress of human civilization originated in India much before corresponding developments in Europe. The ancient Indians in their pursuits exhibited a true scientific spirit in using their knowledge

to the service of humanity. It is not unlikely that in medieval India knowledge of some of the technological practices came from neighbouring countries, but the Indian craftsmen acquired greater skill and mastery over them and even made innovations in course of time so that the Indian products like metals, silk, cotton, paper, cosmetics, perfumes, dyestuffs, glass, porcelain goods, etc., became much valued and preferred articles in many foreign countries those days. Many of the *Yantrams* (apparatus) used by Indian chemists in ancient and medieval periods do have much resemblance to those used in modern times. This is indeed remarkable.

The Age of Decline

A critical evaluation of what led to the decline of science including chemistry in India in later periods is not easy to assess. But there appears to be several factors that may have contributed to the state of stagnation and gradual decay. It has been stated before that since ca. 700-800 A.D. much of the progress in chemistry in India was by the alchemists of the Tantric school of thought that took its root in place of declining Buddhism and Hinduism. The Kings of the Pala dynasty (800-1050 A.D.) were firm believers in the Tantric faith and protectors and promoters of the Tantric cult. Kings of the following Sena dynasty, though Hindus, were also not hostile to the Tantric faith, and there was still general appreciation for scientific knowledge. In many of the treatises of the 4th-7th century A.D., including the *Kamasutra* (ca. 4th century A.D.) of Vatsayana, we find recognition of several arts (kala i.e., skill) which includes the professional skill

of the *dhatuvid* (metallurgist) and those skillful in metal purification and metal working. The attitude was also very scientific and rational in earlier days. Thus, according to Susruta, dissection of the dead body of a human is a must for a student of anatomy and surgery. But such scientific attitude gradually changed since the time of Manu (of early Christian period) who considered that even touching a dead body contaminates the body and soul of a living being, and since the time of Vagbhata even handling of a lancet was discouraged. The Mohammedan invasions since the 12th century A.D. led to destruction of the great centres of learning and large scale devastation of the country and consequent social unrest that was not congenial for any development in science. Parallel to this, due to their occult alchemical practices and beliefs, the chemists fell to disgrace in the Society. Also with the decline of Buddhism there was an emergence of decadent and degenerated Hinduism under priestly dispensation which discouraged rationality and reasoning with its consequent adverse effect on the progress of science. All such factors had their cumulative effect contributing to stagnation and decay in the pursuit of science in India since ca. 14th century A.D. During this time the situation in Europe was not much different. But the birth of a galaxy of talented men there not only saved the situation but helped to usher in the emergence of modern science, the impact of which was felt in India during the British rule. But the question that remains not fully answered is why such a *renaissance* did not happen in India which was the birth place and nursery of science in ancient times.